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Field Trip A Pre-Congress

The "Ligurian Knot": from the Piedmont Tertiary Basin, through the Alpine and Apennine tectonic units to the Ligurian ophiolites

Field Trip Guide

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Foreword

The aim of this excursion is to give an introduction view of the geology of the junction area between the Alps and Apennines. What is the boundary between the two orogens? How did the Alps and the Apennines evolved and/or interacted during time?

These two questions represent the core of a still ongoing debate started at the beginning of last century. This guide-book includes a short outline of how its Authors have faced the problem in the last decades, pointing out the still unsolved and/or newly open problems.

This Guide-book also includes an almost complete reference list of papers (from historical time to now) dealing with the subject.

For people interesting in run the field trip by themselves the following guide-books could be also of interest:

- Vanossi et al 1990 Alpi Liguri, Guide Geologiche Regionali, vol. 2, Società Geologica Italiana, BE-MA Editrice, Milano, 293 pp.
- Abbate E. (1992) - Guida alla Traversata dell'Appennino Settentrionale. Società Geologica Italiana - 76a Riunione Estiva - Firenze 16-20 Settembre 1992. Società Geologica Italiana - Università di Firenze, Firenze, 262 pp.
- Bortolotti V. (1992) - Appennino Tosco-Emiliano, Guide Geologiche Regionali, vol. 4. Società Geologica Italiana, BEMA Editrice, Milano, 329 pp.
- Zanzucchi G. 1994 Appennino Ligure-Emiliano, Guide Geologiche Regionali, vol. 6. Società Geologica Italiana, BEMA Editrice, Milano, 381 pp.
- Tribuzio, R., Molli, G., Riccardi, M.P., Messiga, B. 1997. Third Day. Polyphase metamorphism in ophiolitic gabbros from Bonassola (Internal Liguride Units, Northern Apennines): a record of Western Tethys oceanization. *Ofoliti*, 22(1), 163-174.
- Molli G. (2002) - Field Trip Eastern Liguria/Alpi Apuane. Gordon Research Conference on Rock Deformation. Il Ciocco, Barga, Italy.
- Tribuzio R., Sanfilippo A., Garzetti F., Renna, M.R., Molli, G., Borghini, G., 2009 Rampone, E. Pre-conference field-trip to the Ligurian ophiolites Liguria (Italy), Alpine Ophiolites and Modern Analogues Continental rifting to oceanic lithosphere: insights from the Alpine ophiolites and modern oceans Parma (Italy), September 28-29, 2009 Field trip Guide book, 25 pp.
- Marroni et al . (2004), Field Trip Guide Book - P38. I n: L. Guerrieri, I . Rischia & L. Serva (Eds.), 32 o International

Geological Congress, Florence 20-28 August 2004, *Memorie Descrittive della Carta Geologica d'Italia*, vol. 63, pp. 1-40. Servizio Geologico, d'Italia, Roma.

- Conti P., Conticelli S., Cornamusini G. & Marroni M. (2022) - Toscana, Guide Geologiche Regionali, vol. 15. Società Geologica Italiana, Roma, 375 pp.
- Piana, F., Barale, L., Borghi, A., Carosi, R., d'Atri, A., Fioraso, G., Mosca, P., Vaggelli, G., (2023) - Piemonte, Guide Geologiche Regionali, vol. 16. Società Geologica Italiana, Roma, 399 pp.
- Di Giulio A., Marini, M., Felletti, F., Patacci, M., Massimo Rossi, M., Amadori, C., Menegoni, N., Reguzzi, Silvia Tamburelli, S.(2024) Basin toography and depositional styles controlled by collisional tectonics in the Alps-Apennines junction (Tertiary Piedmont Basin, NW Italy). *Geol. F. Trips Maps*, Vol.16 No.1.2 (2024), 58 pp., 42 figs., 2 tabs. (<https://doi.org/10.3301/GFT.2024.02>).

The excursion is divided in three days:

- a) the first day is dedicated to the introduction of the Tertiary Piemonte Basin;
- b) the second day will focus on the Sesri Voltaggio Zone: the tradional area indicated as the Alps/Apennines boundary;
- c) the third day deals with the geology of the ophiolitic units of the inner Northern Apennines in eastern Liguria a classical site for the study of ophiolites.

Most of the sites we will visit represent actual or potential geosites, therefore please don't use the hammer where you can avoid it. Please leave the exposures as we had inherited it. Nature and future students will be grateful to you!

We wish you an interesting excursion.

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Part I

Geological overview

The Western Alps-Northern Apennine junction area: a regional review

1.1 Introduction

The Alps and the Apennines are two mountain ranges that belong to the central-western Mediterranean region (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). For a long time, differences and transition between the two ranges, which at least partially both face to the Po Plain, have been discussed considering them as independent geological domains. On the contrary they represent part of a continuous orogenic system derived from a complex space-time interaction between the two major European and Adria plates, and intervening oceanic domains and minor microcontinents and or extensional allochthons. Past and present-day geological features of the Alps/Apennines junction area show structures and basin sedimentation history associated with complex interfering processes developed during successive stages of growth of the orogens related with subduction frames which changed and reversed during time.

The relationships between the Western Alps and the Northern Apennines represent a classical and still debated issue in the geology of the Central Mediterranean (ARGAND, 1924; STAUB, 1928; ELTER *et alii*, 1966; LAUBSCHER, 1971; HACCARD *et alii*, 1972; ELTER & PERTUSATI, 1973; DEBELMAS, 1986; CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2008; HANDY *et alii*, 2010; MOLLI *et alii*, 2010; MALUSÀ *et alii*, 2015; SCHMID *et alii*, 2017; PIANA *et alii*, 2017b; VAN HINSBERGEN *et alii*, 2020; MARTINOD *et alii*, 2024; BRUNSMANN *et alii*, 2024) which finds in the NW parts of the Italian peninsula the topical ground for the discussion. The present knowledge of the subject derives from more than one century of research (see historical reviews in GELATI & PASQUARÈ 1970; CASTELLARIN 2001; MOLLI *et alii* 2010) whose main steps are hereafter reported.

In the 19th century the problem was principally faced from a lithologic point of view highlighting the presence of mainly metamorphic rocks as characteristic of the Alps, in contrast to widespread exposures of sedimentary rock-types in the Apennines.

With the recognition (ARGAND, 1924) of nappe architecture for the Alps, STAUB (1928) pointed out the identity of structural zones in the two orogens (Penninic of the Alps correlated with the metamorphic units exposed in the tectonic window of the inner Apennines (e.g. the Alpi Apuane). Whereas, structural

elements as the orogen-scale vergences were quoted as the key for distinction between the two chains (STILLE, 1924). At this time it was pointed out that the western vergences as characteristic of the Alps, whereas the opposite i.e. eastern vergences can be observed in the Apennines.

In all these early interpretations, the Sestri/Voltaggio line (east of Genoa) was recognized as a key structural element defining the boundary between the Alps and the Apennines.

The role of the Sestri/Voltaggio line has been later discussed/undermined taking into account the basin sediments unconformably sealing the internal structures of the zone itself, as well as the surrounding (west and east) metamorphic and unmetamorphic units (ELTER & PERTUSATI, 1973; STURANI, 1973; LAUBSCHER, 1988).

The opposite-dipping subduction frame of the Alps and Apennines and their complex geometric and kinematic interactions

Fig. 1 – Tectonic setting of Central Western Mediterranean and surrounding orogens and basins. SVL, Sestri-Voltaggio line, traditional surface boundary between Alps and Apennines. The white rectangle figured the Field trip's area.

Fig. 2 – Tectonic map of the Western Alps - Northern Apennine junction area. CMA Cottian-Maritime Alps; LA Ligurian Alps; NA Northern Apennine; LPB Liguro-Provençal basin (dark blue oceanic crust); NTS Northern Tyrrhenian sea. In the map the main tectonic and lithostratigraphic units of the system are shown. For the Western Alps: (1,2) Europe-derived external Alpine units and external part of Corsica. 1) Alpine foreland units; (2) External massifs (Ar, Argentera and P, Pelvoux); (3) Middle Permian Briançonnais nappes in the Alps and the Tenda unit in Corsica (4) Middle Permian Internal Massif (DM, Dora Maira and GP, Gran Paradiso); (5) Upper Permian Helminthoid Flysch: UE, Ubaye-Embrunais, Western Liguria Helminthoid Flysch (WL), and the Antola unit (A). With the same color are also represented the ophiolitic non-metamorphic unit of Chenaillot (Ch) and Sesri Voltaggio Zone (SVZ) and in Corsica Balagne (Ba), Nebbio (Ne) and Macinaggio (Ma) units; (6) Schistes Lustrés composite nappe system; (7) Sesia and related units (“lower Austroalpine nappes”); (8) Adria lower crust of the Southern Alps (Ivrea); (9) Adria upper crust basement and cover of the Southern Alps; Northern Apennine: (10) Internal Ligurian units; Il; (11) External Ligurian units (EL) and SubLigurian (Canetolo) units; (12, 13, 14) Adria-derived Tuscan and external foreland Umbria-Marche units; (15) Neogene and Quaternary sediments of Po Plain and inner Tuscan; (16) Post-tectonic cover of Tertiary Piemontese basin and Epiligurian units; (17) Magmatic rocks of Southern Tuscany; (18) Post-tectonic cover of Tertiary Tuscan and external foreland Umbria-Marche units; (19) high angle normal and transcurrent faults; (20) Pliocene isobaths (in Km) in the Po Plain and Adriatic sea. After [Mouli et alii \(2010\)](#).

Fig. 3 – Map of crust - mantle configuration of the Western Alps/ Apeninnea junction area. Contour intervals of 2 km. Dashed lines indicate the limits between the European (E), Adriatic (A) and Ligurian-Tyrrhenian (L-T) Moho. The Ivrea geophysical body (IV) is also reported. Modified after [MOLLI et alii \(2010\)](#), with references therein. More recent interpretations and references in [MENICHELLI et alii \(2023\)](#). White dashed lines, represent the interpreted outline of crustal relicts part of the former “Mediterranean Alps” affected by Corsica-Sardinia block rotation.

at the surface, represent the main topics of the recent debate ([PRINCIPI & TREVES, 1984](#); [CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008](#); [MOLLI, 2008](#); [VIGNAROLI et alii, 2008](#); [CAPPONI et alii, 2009b](#); [HANDY et alii, 2010](#); [MALUSÀ et alii, 2015](#); [LE BRETON et alii, 2017](#); [PIANA et alii, 2017b](#); [SCHMID et alii, 2017](#); [VAN HINSBERGEN et alii, 2020](#); [MARTINOD et alii, 2024](#)).

The field trip aims at describing some key-characters of the Alps-Apeninnea junction area (“Ligurian Knot” after [LAUBSCHER et alii 1992](#)) to give first order constraints on the relationship between the two mountain belts in space and time.

1.2 Geological setting and deep structures

Presently the Alps and the Apennines represent two independent orogens characterized by opposite tectonic vergence W/NW the former and E/NE the latter, roughly oriented perpendicular to their arcuate trends ([Fig. 1](#)).

Crustal seismic structures and 3D tomographic images draw a south/south-eastward-dipping European crust with a high velocity body related to European-plate subduction below the Alps, and an opposite rather continuous westward dipping structure below the Apennines ([KIRÁLY et alii, 2016](#); [EVA et alii, 2020](#); [HANDY et alii, 2021](#), and references therein, [Fig. 3](#)).

In contrast with the simple crustal and mantle structure, at the surface the Alps/Apeninnea junction is more difficult to define considering:

- at least in part coeval age of tectonic events and deformation structures for the Alps and Apennines;
- the presence of tectonic units with similar lithostratigraphic

features and comparable structural evolution;

- superficial continuities of tectonic units from the Western Alps to the Northern Apennines;
- presence of common sedimentary basins sealing or developing during the structural evolution of the two mountain belts.

As matter of fact, the junction area between the Alps and the Apennines is represented by a wide area which includes three major geomorphological and structural domains ([Fig. 4](#)), each one largely composites from a geological point of view ([MOLLI et alii, 2010](#)).

They correspond to:

- a northern region that comprises former exhumed sectors of the orogenic belt partially subsided during Oligocene-Miocene (Tertiary Piemonte basin) and during the Neogene to form Apennine foredeep resting on the Adria Mesozoic-Paleogene successions and covered by thick alluvial sediments of the Po plain.
- a “S-shaped” mountain range formed by the Maritime, Ligurian Alps and the north-westernmost sector of the Apennines;
- a southern undersea region, the Ligurian Sea, geologically belonging to the Liguro-Provençal basin and to the Northern Tyrrhenian. This domain hidden the original connections between Western Alps, Alpine Corsica and easternmost prolongation of Pyrenees.

1.2.1 The northern domain: The Tertiary Piemonte Basin

The northern domain includes the western termination of the Po Plain ([Fig. 4](#)) a c. 500 Km long east-west trending Neogene basin, bordered to the north by the south-vergent fold and thrust belt, retro-foreland of the Alps (Southern Alps), and to the south by the north/north-east vergent structures of the Apennines ([ROURE et alii, 1990](#); [MOSCA et alii, 2010](#); [TURRINI et alii, 2014](#); [LIVANI et alii, 2023](#)).

The area of interest, can be subdivided from the geomorphological point of view in four main provinces ([Fig. 4](#)): the hilly systems of the Torino Hill-Monferrato to the north and of the Langhe to the south, with their interposed Savigliano and Alessandria plains, in turn separated by the Asti hills.

The domain is characterized in surface and subsurface by exposures of Upper Eocene to Miocene-Pliocene successions of the so called Tertiary Piemonte Basin (TPB).

In its southernmost part (Langhe) the TPB sequence consist of continental to transitional deposits of Late Eocene-Early Oligocene ([LORENZ, 1969](#); [GHIBAUDO et alii, 2019](#), and references therein) followed by shelf to slope marly successions and turbidites which were deposited during Late Oligocene and Early Miocene ([GHIBAUDO et alii, 2019](#)). A shelf environment of the Early Burdigalian is locally documented in the Alto Monferrato area ([D’ATRI, 1990b](#); [PIANA et alii, 1997](#)).

By contrast, the northern TPB exposed in the Torino Hill-Monferrato shows more condensed successions with the lowermost portions consisting of basinal mudstones (Monte Piano Marls), followed in the Oligocene-Miocene shallow water clastic and carbonates facies ([CLARI et alii, 1995](#); [DELA PIERRE et alii, 2002b](#)). Coarse-grained facies characterize the western outcrops (Torino Hill area, [BONSIGNORE et alii 1969](#); [STURANI 1973](#)).

Fig. 4 – Geomorphological-structural domains of the Alps-Appennines junction area.

The southern and northern TPB sequences have in common their uppermost portions generally represented by homogenous marly sediments of Tortonian age, and by discontinuous evaporites and lagoon clays recording the Messinian salinity crisis, often in form of chaotic and/or resedimented assemblages (IRACE *et alii*, 2005; DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2002a). In present outcrop exposures, lowermost Pliocene deposits are typically represented by marine clays followed upward by Pliocene sand-rich marginal marine and Pleistocene to Holocene continental successions (GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019, and references therein).

Whereas the northern TPB sequences of Torino Hill-Monferrato rest on an Helminthoid Flysch in physical continuity with the similar unit of the Northern Apennines (External Ligurian Helminthoid Flysch units see below), the successions exposed in the Langhe basin unconformably rest on the exhumed metamorphic nappe-stack of the LA, the Sestri Voltaggio zone and to the west the Helminthoid Flysch of the Antola Nappe.

1.2.2 The “S-shaped” mountain range: between Alps and Apennine

The “S-shaped” mountain range includes the Maritime Alps (southern part of Western Alps), the Ligurian Alps and the northern sector of the Apennines (Fig. 4). It is continuous from the Argentera-Provence, across the Western and Eastern Liguria to the northern Tuscany.

The Maritime and Ligurian Alps (M-LA)

The Maritime and the Ligurian Alps are made up by tectonic units derived from the major paleogeographic domains of the western Tethys (Fig. 5). From W to E: the European continental margin, the Briançonnais/Sub-Briançonnais domains (distal part of European plate or independent terrane, LEMOINE *et alii* 2000; STAMPFLI *et alii* 1998; SCHMID *et alii* 1996; SCHMID & KISSLING

2000) and finally the Ligurian oceanic realm.

The external units comprise a foreland thrust system, forming the Digne and Castellane-Nice arcs, with Eocene-Oligocene foreland deposits floored by thick Mesozoic carbonates of the Dauphinois-Provençal domain (SINCLAIR, 1997; FORD *et alii*, 2002; D’ATRI *et alii*, 2016). The sediments lay on a Variscan basement and post-Variscan cover exposed in the Argentera Massif (BIGOT-CORMIER *et alii*, 2006; BRUNSMANN *et alii*, 2024).

The Frontal Briançonnais Fault, observable south of Cuneo in the Maritime Alps, juxtaposed Sub-Briançonnais-Briançonnais units on top of cover units of the Argentera Massif.

The Briançonnais units are divided in two groups External and Internal units and are composed of a Pre-Namurian basement (exposed only in the Internal units) volcanic and continental clastic deposits (Permian to early Triassic in age), followed by a detached Meso-Cenozoic cover sequence (CORTESOGNO *et alii*, 1993; SENO *et alii*, 2005; DECARLIS *et alii*, 2013).

The external Briançonnais units display a very low to low grade Alpine metamorphic overprint (anchizone up to greenschist facies) whereas the Internal Briançonnais units reach peak conditions up to $P \approx 1.3$ GPa and $T > 400$ °C (CHIESA *et alii*, 1975; CABELLA *et alii*, 1994; SENO *et alii*, 2005).

The innermost units of the Ligurian Alps are represented by the HP-LT ophiolitic units of the Voltri Massif and by three tectonometamorphic units of ophiolitic and continental origin (i.e. Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte, Gazzo-Isoverde and Figogna units) historically referred to as the Sestri-Voltaggio Zone (CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984).

The Voltri Massif consists of two main tectonometamorphic units (Voltri Unit and Palmaro-Caffarella Unit, CAPPONI & CRISPINI 2008) composed of high pressure metamorphic ophiolites. The ophiolites consist of serpentinites with metagabbros and metabasites, metasediments and mantle peridotites, with peak eclogite (450-500 °C and 1.3-2.0 GPa for the Voltri Unit; MESSIGA & SCAMBELLURI, 1991; LIU *et alii*, 1998; FEDERICO *et alii*,

Fig. 5 – (a) Section of the Ligurian Maritime Alps between the Argentera Massif and the Briançonnais units, after [DEBELMAS \(1974\)](#) modified in [LAGABRIELLE \(2023\)](#). (b) Paleogeographic domain of the European margin to Ligurian ocean. (c) Sedimentary series from different domains of the continental margin and adjacent Ligurian ocean (b,c), modified after [LAGABRIELLE \(2023\)](#) using data from [D’ATRI *et alii*, 2016](#); [MICHARD *et alii*, 2022](#). HF–Helminthoid Flysch, MO–Montenotte, VO–Voltri, PA-C–Palmaro-Caffarella, CRV–Cravasco-Voltaggio, GI–Gazzo-Isoverde, F–Figogna Unit.

2005) or blueschist (c.a. 350-400 °C and 1.2 GPa for the Palmaro-Caffarella Unit; [DESMONS *et alii*, 1999](#)) alpine metamorphism, strongly overprinted by greenschist facies fabrics ([CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2002](#)).

The Gazzo-Isoverde Unit (GIU) and the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit (CVMU) are separated from the Voltri Massif by the Sestri-Voltaggio Line ([CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984](#)) that at present is a steeply dipping NS oriented km-scale fault. The main phase deformations predated the Oligocene, since the main structures are sealed by the Oligocene-Miocene formations of the Tertiary Piemontese Basin, even if later reactivations can be observed locally (see below). To the east the units of the Sestri-Voltaggio zone are in contact with very low-grade flysch units (Ronco, Mignanego and Montanesi Units, [CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008](#)) and the unmetamorphosed Antola flysch unit (see below).

The Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit and the Figogna Unit are metaophiolitic units and are re-equilibrated respectively in low-T blueschist facies ($T= 300-350^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $P_{\min}= 0.8-1.0$ GPa for the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit; [CABELLA *et alii*, 1994](#); [DESMONS *et alii*, 1999](#)) and pumpellyite-actinolite facies conditions ($T= 300-350^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $P= 0.7$, [DESMONS *et alii*, 1999](#)). The Gazzo-Isoverde Unit comprises carbonate rocks and shales of Triassic to early Jurassic age, which attained the same blueschist facies metamorphic conditions of the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit. The Figogna Unit shows a polyphase structural evolution but developed at lower metamorphic conditions.

The timing of the high pressure metamorphic events in the internal units of the Ligurian Alps are constrained between ca. 50 Ma (eclogite facies) and 40 Ma (blueschist facies) in metaophiolitic

rocks ([FEDERICO *et alii*, 2005, 2007, Fig. 6](#)). Greenschist-facies retrogression during exhumation is locally dated at ca. 33 Ma ([FEDERICO *et alii*, 2005](#)). For the SVZ adequate absolute time constraints for the Alpine deformational events are still lacking.

The Northern Apennines (NA)

The Northern Apennines are characterized by stacked units ([Fig. 7](#)) belonging to a former accretionary wedge (Ligurian and sub-Ligurian Units) formed during the Cretaceous-Tertiary closure stages of the Ligurian Tethys ocean, overlying the continental derived thrust-sheets and cover nappes of the Adria continental margin of Tuscan and Umbria-Marche Domains (e.g. Elter 1975; Bernoulli 2001; Carmignani, Kligfield, 1990; Butler *et al.* 2006; Molli 2008; Malavieille *et al.* 2016; Schmid *et al.* 2017).

The emplacement of Ligurian prism on top of Sub-Ligurian and Adria-continental margin occurred since Oligocene defines the inception of Apennines-related deformation history.

The uppermost units of the nappe stack are represented by the Ligurian units, the main focus of this Field Trip.

The Ligurian units are subdivided on the basis of stratigraphic and structural features into two main groups ([ELTER, 1975](#)) well defined in the Ligurian-Emilian Apennine: the Internal Ligurian Units (IL) and the External Ligurian units (EL).

The first are characterized by the presence of ophiolites and an Upper Jurassic to Lower Cretaceous sedimentary cover (cherts, Calpionella limestone and Palombini shales) associated with Upper Cretaceous-Paleocene turbiditic sequences ([MOLLI, 2008](#), and references therein). The Internal Ligurian units are considered as remnants of the Liguro-Piemontese ocean or Ligurian Tethys.

Fig. 6 – Compilation of age data from the Voltri Ophiolite and Tertiary Piedmont Basin, after *STARR et alii* (2020). (a) Data compilation shown in map form, indicating the age and the location of the dated sample. The interpretation of the metamorphic facies that is recorded by each age (i.e. recording mineral growth during eclogite, blueschist or greenschist facies conditions) is indicated by the shape and internal colour of the symbols (see key on right). The method used to obtain each age is indicated by the colour of the symbol rim (see key on right). (b) Age plot showing a full compilation of age data, split by unit (TPB, Voltri-Rossiglione meta-sediments, Voltri unit split by area).

Fig. 7 – Schematic sedimentary sequences of the main tectonic systems of the Northern Apennine and related paleotectonic setting. (1) ophiolitic basement: (1a) mantle serpentinites, (1b) gabbros, (1c) basalts, (1d) continental granites (in the External Ligurian units); (2) Cherts; (3) Calpionella limestones; (4) Palombini shales; (5) Val Lavagna schists; (6) Gottero sandstones; (7) Bocco/Colli Tavarone schists; (8-9) Casanova melange and sandstones; (10) Ostia/Scabiazza sandstones; (11) Varicoloured shales with Salti del Diavolo Conglomerates, (11a), Montoggio shales; (12) Helminthoid Flysch, (12a) Antola Flysch; (13) Viano/Signano shales, (13a) Pagliaro shales; (14) Val Sporzana fm.; (15) Canetolo fm. (limestone and shale), Groppo del Vescovo and Vico Flysch; (16) Aveto/ Petrignacola/Bratica sandstones and Coli/Marra marls; (17) continental “Verrucano” and marine transgressive deposits on Hercynian and post-Hercynian units; (18) evaporites and dolomites; (19) Rhaetavícula contorta limestone and marls; (20) Massiccio limestone; (21) Rosso Ammonitico; (22) cherty limestone; (23) Posidonia marls; (24) Cherts; (25) Maiolica; (26) Scaglia Toscana, Scisti a Fucoidi, Scaglia Umbra and Bisciario; (27) siliciclastic turbidites (Macigno, PseudoMacigno, Cervarola, Marnoso-Arenacea, Laga). After [MOLLI \(2008\)](#).

The External Ligurian Units are, on the other hand, distinguishable for the presence of the typical Cretaceous-Paleocene calcareous dominant sequences (the Helminthoid Flysch) associated with complexes or pre-flysch formations called “basal complexes”.

According to their stratigraphic differences, within the EL two main subgroups of units can be recognized ([MOLLI, 1996](#); [MARRONI *et alii*, 1998](#), and references therein): (i) those associated with ophiolites and with ophiolite derived debris, and others (ii) without ophiolites and associated with fragments of Mesozoic sedimentary sequences and conglomerates with Adria affinity ([STURANI \(1973\)](#); [ZANZUCCHI \(1988\)](#); [MOLLI \(1996\)](#)).

Because of their age ([ELTER *et alii*, 1966](#); [WILDI, 1985](#); [ZANZUCCHI, 1988](#); [DANIELE & PLESI, 2000](#)) and composition, these coarse grained conglomerates (Salti del Diavolo Conglomerates) have been compared since the early 1970s with those of Prealpes Romandes (Mocausa conglomerates of the Simme Flysch) implying a common source-area and therefore a common paleotectonic

setting on the distal side of the Adria continental margin ([ELTER, 1997](#); [STAMPFLI *et alii*, 1998](#); [LEMOINE *et alii*, 2000](#), and references therein).

As a whole, the External Ligurian units can be regarded as relics of the former ocean-continent transition area and of the distal Adria continental margin in the Apennines transect ([MOLLI, 1996](#); [MARRONI *et alii*, 1998](#)).

The IL units were affected by polyphase deformation with peak metamorphic P-T conditions of very-low to sub-greenschist facies (prehnite-pumpellyite in metabasic rocks). Recently, however, [MENEHINI *et alii* \(2023\)](#) and [SANITÀ *et alii* \(2024\)](#) suggested at least locally HP/LT peak ($T=230-300$ °C; $P=0.6-0.9$ GPa). On the other hand the EL units were deformed at more shallow structural levels (diagenesis-anchizone transition in pelites).

Among the Ligurian units, the Antola Nappe deserves a special mention. From the lithostratigraphic point of view, the unit can be correlated with the External Ligurian units Helminthoid Flysch ([ABBATE & SAGRI, 1984](#); [CERRINA FERONI *et alii*, 2002](#);

LEVI *et alii*, 2006), even though it occupies a structural position at the top of the IL units, in contrast to the other EL units which are structurally below.

Moreover, it is classically correlated with the Helminthoid Flysch of the Ligurian and Maritime Alps and therefore played a special, still non well understood, role during the pre-Oligocene evolution of the Alps/Apennine orogenic system (ELTER & PERTUSATI, 1973; ELTER, 1997; CORSI *et alii*, 2001; LEVI *et alii*, 2006).

On top of EL units and Antola nappe the deposits of the Epiligurian Succession may be considered as the distal-lateral portion of the time-equivalent TPB. They consist mainly of terrigenous clastics even if they include facies ranging from pelagic and hemipelagic deposits to siliciclastic turbidites and to shelf sandstones and calcarenites. The Epiligurian Succession is characterized by ages ranging from Middle Eocene to Late Miocene-Pliocene and overlies the at least in part already deformed Ligurian Units.

From a stratigraphic point of view, the Epiligurian Succession consists of unconformity-bounded units whose limits (major unconformities) are strongly controlled by sub-marine tectonics which often generated slumpings and olistostromes (sedimentary melanges).

Five major unconformities define the main lithostratigraphic units (Monte Piano, Ranzano; Antognola, Bismantova, Termina, Gessoso-solfifera and Argille Azzurre formations).

The oldest two unconformities (Monte Piano and Ranzano) may be used to define:

- the end of “Alpine”-related deformations, subduction and exhumation up to the surface of the Ligurian Alps nappe stack, Sestri Voltaggio zone and overlying Ligurian and Antola units;
- the beginning of deformation events related to the Apenninic-related geodynamics.

The younger unconformity within the Epiligurian basins may be related to surface response of Apennines wedge growth and NNE-verging migration of the orogen which progressively incorporated the foredeep units of the Adria continental margin.

The southern domain: the Liguro-Provençal and Northern Tyrrhenian basins

The southern domain includes an undersea region geologically belonging to two different geological provinces: the Liguro-Provençal basin and the northern part of the Tyrrhenian basin (Fig. 2, Fig. 7).

Both basins are interpreted as Late Oligocene to Miocene backarcs developed in relationships with Apulian westward subduction and eastward slab retreat (LAUBSCHER, 1988; PATACCA & SCANDONE, 1989; DOGLIONI *et alii*, 1999; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2008). These basins are therefore parts of the Apennines geodynamic system, and developed during its successive stages of evolution (GUEGUEN *et alii*, 1998; FACCENNA *et alii*, 1997; JOLIVET *et alii*, 1998; LE BRETON *et alii*, 2021).

The rifting stages in the Liguro-Provençal basin are dated to Oligocene to Early Miocene (Aquitania-early Burdigalian) and were associated with calcalkaline magmatism on land (LUSTRINO & WILSON, 2007). The following oceanic spreading (drift-

ing stage) occurred in the Burdigalian (19-16 Ma) with formation of an atypical oceanic crust (GUEGUEN *et alii*, 1998; FANUCCI & MORELLI, 2003; ROLLET *et alii*, 2002; JOLIVET *et alii*, 2020) characterized by discontinuous tholeiitic volcanic edifices settled within the exhumed mantle, related with slow-to very slow tectonically controlled oceanic spreading (CHAMOT-ROOKE *et alii*, 1999; SÉRANNE, 1999; ROLLET *et alii*, 2002; JOLIVET *et alii*, 2020).

The drifting stage and oceanic accretion were associated with the anticlockwise Corsica-Sardinia block-rotation of 30° (SPERANZA *et alii*, 2002; MAFFIONE *et alii*, 2008) or 45-50° (GATTACCECA *et alii*, 2007). The rotation occurred after Aquitanian and was essentially completed at about 15 Ma according to (GATTACCECA *et alii*, 2007). A third of the total amount of rotation occurred at a rate of c.15°/Ma between 20.5 and 18 Ma. Relevant to be noted that paleomagnetic data of BORMIOLI & LANZA (1995), CARRAPA *et alii* (2003) and MAFFIONE *et alii* (2008) in lower Oligocene-Middle Miocene sediments of TPB documented counterclockwise rotation (up to c. 50°) (with respect to Africa) during the same Aquitanian-Serravalian time, thus supporting the idea that the TPB basin and Corsica-Sardinia block jointly rotated as a whole.

A still debated issue with relevant implication for kinematic reconstructions, hinge on whether Sardinia-Corsica was attached to the Provence in southern France or was part of Iberia (STAMPFLI *et alii*, 2002; ROSENBAUM *et alii*, 2002; HANDY *et alii*, 2010; ADVOKAAT *et alii*, 2014; VAN HINSBERGEN *et alii*, 2014; LE BRETON *et alii*, 2021; SIRAVO & SPERANZA, 2024). The assumption that Corsica-Sardinia block was attached to southern France imply a post early Eocene and pre-Oligocene c.45° ccw rotation relative to Eurasia with relevant implication for Alps-Apennines junction area history (SCHMID *et alii*, 2017; VAN HINSBERGEN *et alii*, 2020; LE BRETON *et alii*, 2021; MANTOVANI *et alii*, 2023).

1.3 Final remarks

The present-day morpho-structural domains of the Western Alps/Northern Apennine junction area result from a kinematically complex interaction between interfering orogenic systems related to the opposite-dipping east-southeast “Alpine” and west-northwest “Apennine” subductions. Within the junction area reworked and reactivated structures of a formerly continuous Late Cretaceous/mid-Eocene intraoceanic and continental subduction-related “Alpine” system are preserved. They presently are exposed in the Ligurian Alps and became part of the the younger “apenninic” system after being incorporated since Aquitanian during the Corsica-Sardina block rotation.

The shallow and deep configuration and related structural zones of the Western Alps/Northern Apennines junction area are therefore the result of different orogenic processes such as the collisional indentation of Europe and Adria plates (40-35 Ma); the development of structures related with the opposite dipping “Alpine and “Apennines” subductions after a subduction reversal (35-33 Ma) and the kinematic development of the northern segment of the Apennines in a frame of Adria slab retreat to which the opening of the backarc Liguro-Provençal basin (33-23 Ma) and Corsica-Sardinia and joined Ligurian Alps-TPB block rotation (23-15 Ma) occurred.

Part II

Field Trip

Day 1 : Eastern Tertiary Piemonte Basin

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Geological overview

This first part of the Field Trip will focus on the syn-orogenic basin system developed since the late Eocene - early Oligocene at the junction between the two orogens. The sedimentary successions of these basins recorded the main stages of the Western Alps (neoAlpine events) and Apennines tectonic evolution, whose evidence, mostly represented by regional-scale unconformities, can be correlated within each basin and, partially, across them.

The field trip runs through the Tertiary Piemonte Basin (TPB), whose successions were deposited in the southern part of the Alpine retroforeland realm since the Late Eocene up to the Messinian (Fig. 8). Although the TPB differentiated in partially independent sub-basins, it recorded well, as a unique syn-orogenic basin system for the Alps and Apennines orogens, the entire geodynamic history of the Adria-Europe collision in NW Italy. The TPB went from being an Alpine retroforeland basin to being a thrust-top Apennines basin system, as the Western Mediterranean geodynamics experienced the change in the continental subduction polarity and the onset of the Ligurian-Balearic oceanic spreading.

An overview of the TPB stratigraphy and tectono-sedimentary evolution will be provided by visiting some representative outcrops and landscapes. An interpretive synthesis will be given as grounded on calibration of surface geological features, traced at regional scale on continuous geologic maps, with some seismic sections that cross the whole TPB succession for more than one hundred km. The data integration process provides constraints for critical discussion on the evolution of the Alps-Apennines interference zone.

The Tertiary Piemonte Basin (TPB)

South of the Po River, the successions of the TPB crop out in different geologic domains (Torino Hill, Monferrato, Monregalese, Langhe, Alto Monferrato, and Borbera-Grue) and are recognizable in the subsurface (to the depth of 4-6 kilometres). These successions mask both the tectonic boundaries between the metamorphic units of the Alpine axial sector, the Ligurian units (i.e.: the non-metamorphic sedimentary units belonging to the eastern margin of the Liguria-Piemonte domain) and the paleo-Adriatic margin units (CASSANO *et alii*, 1986; FALLETTI *et alii*, 1995; MUTTI *et alii*, 1995; PIANA & POLINO, 1995; BIELLA *et alii*, 1997; PIANA, 2000; MOSCA, 2006; MOLLI *et alii*, 2010; PIANA *et alii*, 2017a; ROSSI, 2017; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019; GHIELMI *et alii*, 2019)

Although strongly differentiated by synorogenic tectonics, these successions were deposited in a single, long-lived (late Eocene-Miocene) and poly-historic (sensu KINGSTON *et alii*, 1983) sedimentary basin, affected by coeval tectonic and depositional events in all its parts, which are marked by unconformities physically traceable at a regional scale, each bounding major, regional scale synthems, whose ages and distribution are reported in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10.

The TPB underwent a complex evolution, marked by a high tectonic mobility reflecting the geodynamic reorganization of the central Mediterranean area during Oligocene and Miocene times (MUTTI *et alii*, 2002; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019). This is documented by its stratigraphic architecture, which records multi-stage migrations of the source areas and depocenters with time, originating a complex distribution of terrigenous depositional systems (MUTTI *et alii*, 2002), developed as a response to local or regional uplift and subsidence events. These events occurred in a different way and at different extent in the several subdomains into which TPB can be subdivided, leading to the deposition of a complex setting of laterally changing lithostratigraphic units, which have been classified in the last decades with different names and partially different criteria.

The main post-Eocene tectonic stages in the TPB stratigraphic record

During the middle Eocene-Messinian time interval, the syn-orogenic basins of the Alps-Apennines interference zone formed

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Fig. 8 – (a) Tectonic sketch-map of the Alps-Apennines junction zone. Legend: CL: Canavese Line; IV: Ivrea-Verbano Zone; LG: Granite of the South Alpine “Lake District”; Go: outcropping Gonfolite s.l. successions; SA: Southern Alps; GP: Gran Paradiso polymetamorphic Massif; SL: Sesia-Lanzo Unit (AustroAlpine Domain); Ca: Canavese Zone; La: Lanzo Ultramafic Massif; AMB: Ambin polymetamorphic Massif; PieZ: Piemonte Zone; DM: Dora Maira polymetamorphic Complex; WLig: Western Ligurian Units; Br: Briançonnais Domain; BLv, BLs, BLb: metavolcanics (v), sedimentary and metasedimentary successions (s), polymetamorphic basement (b) of the Ligurian-Briançonnais Domain; Vo: Voltri metaophiolite Massif; SVZ: Sestri-Voltaggio Zone; LIG: undifferentiated Ligurian units; Sli: Sub-Ligurian Units; AF: Eocene-Oligocene successions of the Alpine Foreland Basin; DP: Dauphinois-Provençal Domain; AR: Argentera Massif; PF: Penninic Front (Internal Briançonnais Front); CL: Canavese Line; SB, AB: Savigliano and Alessandria Basin; MR, LA, AM, BG, TH and MO: Monregalese, Langhe, Alto Monferrato, Borbera-Grue, Torino Hill and Monferrato TPB sub-domains; EL: Epi-Ligurian units; PI: Pliocene deposits. Red lines: main subsurface fault systems: CVF: Cavour transpressive fault; SBT: San Benigno thrust; SST: Salussola thrust; VFT: Vercelli-Treccate fault; PTF: Padane (Apennines) Thrust Front; SLT: Savigliano-Moretta thrust system; TNF: Tanaro Fault system (sensu [GHIELMI et alii, 2019](#)). Blue lines: surface fault systems: SFT: Scriveria Fault; VV: Villalvernia-Varzi Fault; RF: Rio Freddo Deformation Zone and Villadeati fault system. The grey lines bounding the yellow-green contoured areas refer to the depth in metres of the subsurface base of the Pliocene successions (after [BIGI et alii, 1990](#)). The inset map of Piemonte region in the upper left corner reports the trace of the regional cross-section and the three main structural subdivisions of the Western Alps: Legend: BI: Biella, TO: Torino, AL: Alessandria, CN: Cuneo. (b) Regional-scale, geological cross-section. Legend: CZ, Canavese Zone; IVZ, Ivrea-Verbano Zone; LIG, non metamorphic Ligurian units; O-M BTP, Oligocene-Miocene succession of Tertiary Piemonte Basin; O-M GB, Oligocene-Miocene succession of the Gonfolite Basin; LIG OPH, Ligurian ophiolites and metaophiolites (MA LIG); P-Q, Pliocene-Quaternary succession; SA, Mesozoic sedimentary successions of the SouthAlpine domain and subsurface Adria crust; SLZ, Sesia-Lanzo Zone; SVZ, Sestri-Voltaggio Zone. Mainly after [CASSANO et alii \(1986\)](#); [BIELLA et alii \(1988, 1997\)](#); [FALETTI et alii \(1995\)](#); [ROURE et alii \(1996\)](#); [SCHMID et alii \(2004, 2017\)](#); [MOSCA et alii \(2010\)](#).

Fig. 9 – Chronostratigraphic framework of the TPB and Pliocene synthems and relevant unconformities. After PIANA *et alii* (2017a).

Fig. 10 – Distribution of the synthems into which the Pliocene and Tertiary Piemonte Basin (TPB) sedimentary successions have been subdivided. After PIANA *et alii* (2017a).

through three main tectono-sedimentary stages each one consisting of some steps and several Geologic Events that are recognizable at regional scale.

Stage 1 (Alpine stage)

A first major stage (“Alpine stage”, middle Eocene - Aquitanian) was coeval with the collisional evolution of the Alpine belt, whose control on the sedimentation was recorded with major effects in the Alpine Foreland Basin and, with a lesser extent, also in the retro-foreland domains. In this stage the TPB can be considered as an epiMesoAlpine basin system (sensu MUTTI *et alii*, 1995).

Stage 1a - Continuum of the Alpine collisional tectonics and beginning of local transtensional regime (lower part of Rupelian)

The continuum of the collisional contractional tectonics (“Ligurian phase”), coeval with the westward movement of the Adriatic indenter, induced at shallow crustal levels a complex partitioning of transpressional and transtensional regime, synchronous with the main exhumation phase of the HP metamorphic units of the SW Alps, as largely described in literature (HOGERDUIJN STRATING, 1991; RUBATTO & SCAMBELLURI, 2003; CARRAPA *et alii*, 2003; FEDERICO *et alii*, 2004, 2005; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2008, 2009, 2010; MOSCA *et alii*, 2010; ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; ARGNANI, 2012; BEUCHER *et alii*, 2012; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2014).

The Rupelian tectonic phase, mostly transpressional in the overall southern part of the Western Alps (e.g., DUMONT *et alii*, 2012), can be related in TPB to a local transtensional regime developed in the inner side of the uplifting Alpine belt.

High angle, synsedimentary faults dissected the units of the TPB substratum in a series of fault blocks (MUTTI *et alii*, 2002). A marked regional uplift occurred, followed by an intense regional denudation, which resulted, during the Rupelian, in widespread coarse-grained sedimentation (either continental or marine) over the exhumed basement (BERTOTTI *et alii*, 2006; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2010).

A marked transgressive event (LORENZ, 1969; HACCARD *et alii*, 1972) occurred in the internal part of the Alpine belt. This occurred in an overall geomorphological context marked by fast uplifting areas and adjoining throughs, with subsidence rates highly variable through space and time.

In the TPB the stage 1a induced the sedimentation of *Sub-synthem TPB 1a*, bounded at the base by the Unconformity D1 (lower part of Rupelian), which, in the southern part of the TPB, consists of a nonconformity surface between the bedrock (either metamorphic or non-metamorphic) and the overlying sedimentary successions. In the northern part of the TPB, it consists of an angular unconformity between the Priabonian marly successions of Synthem TPB 0 and the shallow water coarse-grained deposits of the base of Synthem TPB 1. This begins with continental to shallow water Rupelian conglomerates and arenites (Molare Fm., LORENZ, 1969; Cardona Fm., CLARI *et alii*, 1987; Savignone Fm., BELLINZONA & BONI, 1971, that grade to sandy and muddy sediments, i.e. the lower part of Rigoroso-Rocchetta Fm. (GELATI, 1968) in Langhe and Alto Monferrato, and the Monastero Fm. (BELLINZONA & BONI, 1971) in Borbera-Grue sub-domain.

Stage 1b - Transtensional regime and related subsidence (late

Rupelian - Aquitanian)

This tectonic phase is related with the bending of the Adriatic continental margin, which created the space for the sedimentation in the early stages of the Apennine foredeep evolution.

The westward subduction of the Adria crust (“Apennines subduction”) induced the inflection of the Adriatic margin and caused a general extension in the internal part of the Alpine belt (JOLIVET & FACCENNA, 2000; JOLIVET *et alii*, 2009; JOURDAN *et alii*, 2013). This led to the formation of fault-bounded basins which occurred in a context of regional extensional and left-lateral strike-slip faulting (GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019). In this way, the Ligurian Alps belt experienced more than 4 km of subsidence from 30 to 26 Ma (BERTOTTI *et alii*, 2006), whilst in late Oligocene the erosion (JOURDAN *et alii*, 2013) and subsidence rates slowed down to average values.

Step 1b led to a first interaction between the Apennines tectonic fronts, which were progressively migrating toward North and NE, and the Alpine internal boundary faults that were driving the uplifting and back thrusting of the Western Alps.

In the TPB the *Sub-synthem BTP1b* was deposited, which is bounded at the base by local discontinuous unconformities, detectable in seismic sections but not easy to be traced at regional scale. This sub-synthem consists of late Rupelian to Aquitanian hemipelagic slope marls (Antognola Fm, Rigoroso Fm., Rocchetta Fm.) with interbedded arenaceous to conglomeratic resedimented bodies, e.g., Garbagna and Variano member (Rigoroso Fm.) in the Borbera-Grue sub-domain (GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019).

Sub-synthem BTP1b ends with Aquitanian-lower Burdigalian siliceous slope deposits rich in siliceous plankton (e.g., Marne a Pteropodi inferiori, siliceous member of Montechiaro d’Acqui Fm.; (GELATI *et alii*, 2010; CLARI *et alii*, 1987; D’ATRI *et alii*, 2015) due to a paleoceanographic event extended to the whole Mediterranean area.

Stage 2 (Apennine stage)

A second major stage (“Apennine stage”, Burdigalian-Messinian), starting with the opening of the Balearic basin, i.e., when the southern prolongation of the Alpine belt (the “mesoMediterranean plate” sensu CARMINATI & DOGLIONI, 2005) was dismembered by the back-arc extension induced by the onset of the Adriatic (Apennines) subduction (RÉHAULT *et alii*, 1984; JOLIVET & FACCENNA, 2000; ROLLET *et alii*, 2002). This stage continued through the Miocene, as the north-eastward propagation of the Apennines tectonic fronts proceeded. In this way the TPB became a basin system whose sub-domains evolved as thrust-to-top basins on the roof of the Apennine frontal thrust.

Stage 2a - Compressional tectonics at the Burdigalian basin reorganisation

The change in the direction of motion of the Adriatic Indenter (AI) with respect to Europe from NW-ward to WNW-ward at about 20 My (EDEL *et alii*, 2001; SCHMID & KISSLING, 2000; HANDY *et alii*, 2010) resulted in conditions of oblique convergence and increased collisional tectonics, whose effects were recorded in a large part of the Mediterranean area in the lower Burdigalian.

The tectonic indentation of the European and Apulia continental margin caused the switch from transtensional to contractional

and transpressional regime in the TPB, inducing inversion of a great number of tectonic structures (PIANA & POLINO, 1994, 1995; FALLETTI *et alii*, 1995; PIANA *et alii*, 1997; PIANA, 2000; FESTA *et alii*, 2005; PIANA *et alii*, 2006; ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; MAINO *et alii*, 2013; GHIBAUDDO *et alii*, 2019). This process was coeval with the transpressional tectonics recorded in Sardinia and southwestern Corsica (CARMIGNANI *et alii*, 2004, and references therein).

This important tectonic stage was accompanied by significant change in sediment composition within the TPB, as the formerly active lower Oligocene sources, mostly located in the southern areas (Ligurian Alps), gradually moved to the West (CARRAPA, 2002). A marked regional uplift occurred, with subsequent high denudation rates of the West-Alpine axial sector. This resulted in the eastward migration of fan-delta systems, prograding from the western margin of the TPB (the “Saluzzo-Monregalese belt” of ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; CARRAPA *et alii*, 2016).

In this period (Early Miocene) the TPB underwent a rotation of ca. 50° counterclockwise with respect to Africa (MAFFIONE *et alii*, 2008). The counter-clockwise rotation of the Corsica-Sardinia microplate is known to have been accompanied by oceanic spreading and generation of the central oceanic portion of the Ligure-Provençal basin as a back-arc basin in the wake of the south-eastward roll-back of the Apennines-Maghrebides subduction (REHAULT *et alii*, 1984; VIGLIOTTI & LANGENHEIM, 1995; DOGLIONI *et alii*, 1997; GUEGUEN *et alii*, 1998; SPERANZA *et alii*, 2002; FACCENNA *et alii*, 2001; ROLLET *et alii*, 2002; GATTACCECA *et alii*, 2007; CHERCHI *et alii*, 2008; CARMINATI *et alii*, 2012).

GATTACCECA *et alii* (2007) established that approximately 30° of rotation occurred between 20.5 and 18 Ma, that is mostly during the Burdigalian. Volcaniclastic layers found in the Pietra da Cantoni in northern TPB (Monferrato) also date to 18.7 Ma (d’Atri *et al.*, 2001) recording a coeval volcanic activity.

In response to these major tectonic events, a number of regional scale unconformities developed throughout the Alps-Apennines syn-orogenic basins.

In the TPB, the D2 major regional unconformity formed in response to the above-described events. It is an angular unconformity which cuts into the Marne a Pteropodi inferiori/siliceous member of the Montechiaro d’Acqui Fm. and Antognola / Rigoroso formations (Monferrato, Alto Monferrato) and corresponds to a Chattian (or Aquitanian) - lower Burdigalian hiatus. In the deep-water settings (Langhe, Torino Hill), it laterally grades to a correlative conformity, dated to the early Burdigalian (d’Atri *et al.*, 2015). The D2 discontinuity surface formed during the Burdigalian event and led to a major reshaping of the basin (CLARI *et alii*, 1995; FALLETTI *et alii*, 1995; d’ATRI *et alii*, 1997).

The succession deposited during the stage 2a (*Synthem BTP 2*) consists mainly of Burdigalian carbonate ramp deposits passing upward into deeper-water calcareous marls through glauconite-rich outer ramp condensed sediments (e.g. Visone Fm., in Alto Monferrato, Pietra da Cantoni in Monferrato; d’ATRI, 1990a,b; d’ATRI *et alii*, 1997; PIANA *et alii*, 1997; d’ATRI *et alii*, 2015). In the Monregalese mixed siliciclastic-carbonate ramp deposits (San Paolo Fm., CASNEDI & MOSNA, 1970) rest unconformably on Oligocene deposits or directly on the metamorphic substrate. Locally (i.e., in Torino Hill and western Monferrato) Burdigalian-lower Langhian mainly sandy resedimented de-

posits are present (Moransengo Fm, Termofourà Fm, CLARI *et alii*, 1995; DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2003; FESTA *et alii*, 2009). Carbonates and glauconite-rich resedimented arenites, derived by the erosion of the carbonate ramp deposits, form distinct layers at the base of the synthem in the Langhe sub-basin (AMOROSI *et alii*, 1997; GELATI *et alii*, 1998), and in Monferrato (S. Michele Member, DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2003).

Stage 2b - The late Burdigalian TPB inversion and the Langhian-early Tortonian northward shifting of the basin depocenter

Following the early Burdigalian phase of uplift, a major late Burdigalian basin inversion occurred in TPB, leading to a dramatic increase of subsidence rate and accommodation space creation followed by another contractional event which induced, in Langhian and early Serravallian, the underthrusting of the Ligurian and Adria margin units and the uplifting of TPB margins (GNACCOLINI, 1968; GHIBAUDDO *et alii*, 1985; GNACCOLINI & ROSSI, 1994; PIANA & POLINO, 1994; CLARI *et alii*, 1995; MUTTI *et alii*, 1995; DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2002a; ROSSI & CRAIG, 2016; GHIBAUDDO *et alii*, 2019).

This event gave origin to a regional scale discontinuity D3 (late Burdigalian) that is clearly detectable at a seismic scale (Mosca *et al.*, 2009). In Monferrato and Torino Hill, it is an angular unconformity separating the prevalent carbonate deposits of Synthem TPB2, below, from the mixed deposits of *Synthem TPB3a* (Areniti di Tonengo, DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2003; Baldissero Fm., FESTA *et alii*, 2009) above. In the southern TPB, the D3 becomes a correlative conformity at the base of turbidite successions of the Serole, Cortemilia and Costa Aresa formations (GHIBAUDDO *et alii*, 1985; d’ATRI *et alii*, 2015; GHIBAUDDO *et alii*, 2019). The accommodation space increased in the SSW portion of the basin, which became the major depocenter. Consequently, late Burdigalian to early Serravallian depocenters formed in the western TPB, accommodating more than 2800 m of westerly-derived turbidites (e.g., Cortemilia Fm, MUTTI *et alii*, 2002). During this stage, a progressive exhumation of tectonic units of the Alpine poly-metamorphic basement units has continued, inducing general uplifting of the orogenic belt, which in turn was bounding the basin to the SW. This was recorded in TPB as a marked change in the sediment provenances and a consequent change in the sandstone composition, namely a sharp decrease of serpentinite clasts in Cortemilia Formation (gelati). The regional subsidence continued during Langhian with the deposition of marly sediments (e.g., Marna di Paroldo) and siliceous, condensed deposits (e.g., Bistagno Formation, d’ATRI *et alii*, 2015; 2nd siliceous horizon) in the southern TPB.

During Stage 2b the continuing Apennines contractional tectonics led to the underthrusting, at depth, of Ligurian successions resting on the Adria margin below Alpine metamorphic units. This resulted in the formation of a regional scale antiformal stack (FALLETTI *et alii*, 1995), also described as “Alto Monferrato High” in ROSSI *et alii* (2009) and MOSCA *et alii* (2010) or as “Langhe deep structure” (GHIELMI *et alii*, 2019) (see below, seismic transect 7). This caused a new partial basin inversion and the onset of the progressive northward shifting of the TPB main depocenters (ROSSI & CRAIG, 2016; d’ATRI *et alii*, 2015), the uplift of the SW and SE-to-E basin margins and the continuing growth of the Monferrato structural high with relevant major

uplift of the northern TPB margin.

These events induced the local occurrence of angular unconformities during the Langhian (ROSSI & CRAIG, 2016; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019) and the northwestward progradations of slope and shelf sediments (*Synthem TPB 3b*) (Marne di Cessole, Siltiti di Gavi, Serravalle Fm) in Alto Monferrato and Borbera-Grue, making a basinward lateral transition to slope and turbidite deposits in Langhe (Cessole Fm., Cassinasco Fm. and Lequio Fm.). In the northern TPB Serravallian outer platform to slope sediments (Marne di Mincengo, DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2003; FESTA *et alii*, 2009) were deposited. Step 2b ends with a widespread hiatus (i.e., D4 unconformity) to the north and east, and deposition of lower Tortonian outer shelf sediments (lower member of the Marne di S. Agata Fossili; see also GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 1985, 2014) to the south, in Alto Monferrato and Borbera-Grue. The latter interfinger, to the west, with turbidites of the Lequio Fm. at the top of *Synthem BTP 3b*.

Stage 3 - Padane stage

A third Stage (Padane Stage) followed up to the Present, whose early evolutionary steps are reported here below even though not related to the Field Trip stops.

Once that the TPB was quite filled, i.e., during the Messinian evaporitic stage, the persisting collision of the Europe and Adria lithosphere (HANDY *et alii*, 2021) induced a deep physiographic reorganisation during the late Messinian. A rapid exhumation and surface uplift of the Western Alps and Northern Apennines occurred during the Plio-Pleistocene transition, maybe due to, or enhanced by, the detachment of the European slab (Fox *et al.*, 2015) and consequent subhorizontal tearing (LIPPITSCH *et alii*, 2003; KISSLING *et alii*, 2006). Finally, unloading effects due to glacial erosion and melting (CHAMPAGNAC *et alii*, 2004) enhanced the uplifting ratios. These events paved the way to a third stage, the Padane Stage, during which the reorganisation of the synorogenic basins occurred. The post-Miocene Padane tectonics led to a further northward thrusting of the TPB, with minor tilting and limited faulting of the basin at the rear of the Monferrato-Torino Hill frontal thrust system.

The Padane stage reshaping modified only partially the previous TPB physiography, so that the lateral relationships between the Oligocene-Miocene successions of the different subdomains can be still recognized in the field and in the subsurface.

Structural setting of the TPB subdomains

Torino Hill and Monferrato subdomains

In the northwestern edge the TPB succession presently crops out in the NE-SW directed anticline of the Torino Hill, which is bounded on its eastern side by the transpressive Rio Freddo Deformation Zone (RFDZ, PIANA & POLINO, 1994, 1995) that separates it from the Monferrato domain. The RFDZ was active from the early Oligocene until at least the Tortonian (PIANA, 2000) and controlled, together with the Villadeati transpressive fault system (DELA PIERRE *et alii*, 2003), the sedimentary evolution of the Monferrato domain. Both Torino Hill and Monferrato are displaced at depth by the Apennine (Padane) thrust front (CASSANO *et alii*, 1986), active until the early Pleistocene, that

overrode them onto the Neogene and Paleogene successions resting, in their turn, onto the Adria Mesozoic successions, presently placed below the Po plain. For this reason, Torino Hill and Monferrato are often considered as a single tectonic system at the northwestern edge of the Northern Apennines, although they show a different structural setting and pre-Pliocene kinematic evolution. The tectonic-sedimentary evolution of Monferrato was controlled by NW-SE steep fault zones rooted at depth that acted as transpressive faults during the Late Eocene-very early Oligocene, as transtensional faults during the late Rupelian and Chattian and again as mostly contractional faults during the Early Burdigalian, Tortonian and intra-Messinian tectonic stages, prior to the final emplacement due to the Apennine thrust front (PIANA & POLINO, 1995; CLARI *et alii*, 1995; FESTA *et alii*, 2005). The present setting of Torino Hill is due to the activity of NE-SW transpressive faults, rooted in the Alpine metamorphic basement roughly parallel to the inner boundary of the NW Alps (GHIELMI *et alii*, 2019; MOSCA *et alii*, 2010), which induced the growing of the Torino Hill anticline since the late Tortonian, together with marked Plio-Pleistocene uplifting (FORNO *et alii*, 2018). This structural setting ends towards East against the RFDZ, characterized by a complex indentation of the above-described NE-SW contractional faults and the NW-SE transpressive faults of Monferrato (PIANA, 2000), rooted in the Ligurian units of the TPB substratum, which separates the Torino Hill from Monferrato.

Monregalese subdomain

The southwestern part the TPB is represented by the Monregalese (MR) succession resting directly on the basement rocks of the Ligurian Alps and displaced at depth by north-vergent transpressive faults propagating from the bedrock (ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; PIANA *et alii*, 2021).

Langhe subdomain

The Monregalese succession, which lacks a large part of the Oligocene interval, grades to the North into the Langhe domain (LA), which shows the more thick and complete succession of the TPB, since it has been deposited in the more subsiding and deep part of the basin for most of the Oligocene-Miocene time span (ROSSI *et alii*, 2009). The northwestern margin of the Langhe basin is represented, in the subsurface, by the Saluzzo basin margin, which can be considered a transition zone to the Torino Hill domain.

Alto Monferrato subdomain

The eastern and northeastern margins of the Langhe basin are represented by the Alto Monferrato domain (AM), whose succession rests on the Ligurian Alps meta-ophiolites and is less thick and complete with respect to the Langhe one (Fig. 11, Fig. 12). The eastern margin of the Langhe basin was differentiated from the adjoining "Alto Monferrato high" (sensu ROSSI *et alii*, 2009) by the multistage Miocene activity of a major contractional structure rooted in the Adria basement at the depth of more than 4 km (Langhe Deep Structure, sensu GHIELMI *et alii*, 2019).

Fig. 11 – Line Drawing of seismic section across the Torino Hill TPB domain (modified after [COMERCI et alii, 2021](#)).

Fig. 12 – Simplified stratigraphic logs of the successions of the Alto Monferrato (left) and Borbera-Grue (right) TPB subdomains. AGF–Undifferentiated internal Ligurian Units (Cretaceous) FAN= Antola Formation and LID–Bruggi-Selvapiana Formation (Upper Cretaceous), CRA–Breccie della Costa di Cravara (upper Eocene - base Rupelian?); continental deposits, MOR–Molare Formation (Rupelian): continental to marine shallow water and fan delta deposits, SAV–Savignone Formation (Rupelian): continental to fan delta deposits, MST–Monastero Formation (Rupelian): deposits related to hyperpycnal flows with local turbidite layers, RIO–Rigorouso Formation (upper Rupelian-Aquitianian): marly deep water deposits with intercalated arenaceous lenticular resedimented bodies (RIO3a Garbagna lithozone; RIO 3b Variano lithozone).

Fig. 13 – Line drawing across the Borbera-Grue TPB domain. Modified after [ROSSI & CRAIG, 2016](#). Black lines: interpreted faults of the Monferrato thrust front (north-easternmost sector) and Villalvernia-Varzi fault system (VV).

Borbera-Grue subdomain (“Eastern TPB”)

To the East and NE of the present Scrivia valley, i.e., externally to the northern boundary of the exhumed Alpine metamorphic units (Axial Alpine Front in [MOSCA *et alii*, 2010](#), the TPB is represented by the Borbera-Grue domain (BG), whose succession rests on Ligurian non-metamorphic units, which locally overthrust the Oligocene part of the TPB succession itself ([Fig. 13](#), [Fig. 12](#)). The Borbera-Grue domain is bounded to the North by the Villalvernia-Varzi fault system ([BONI, 1961, 1962, 1969; DI GIULIO & GALBIATI, 1995; FESTA *et alii*, 2015](#)), a major transpressive structure that controlled the sedimentary evolution of the eastern TPB during several stages from the early Oligocene to the Late Miocene.

In the Monferrato, Borbera-Grue and Alto Monferrato sub-basins the steps of the regional tectonic evolution at the Alps-Appennines junction are better recorded than in the other sub-domains, due to the abundance of shelf successions marked by regional-scale unconformities ([PIANA *et alii*, 2017a; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019](#)) originated by the activity of contractional faults (e.g. Rio Freddo Deformation Zone, [PIANA & POLINO, 1995; PIANA, 2000](#); Val Gorrini thrust and Grogna thrust Zone, [PIANA *et alii*, 1997, 2006](#)).

Field Trip Route

Tortona - Albarasca - Borghetto Borbera - Sottovalle - Carrosio - Bosio - Voltaggio ([Fig. 14](#)).

Stop 1.1

Locality: Albarasca.

44.754670,8.950913

Topic: Langhian unconformity (D3b), the late Burdigalian TPB inversion and the Langhian-early Tortonian northward shifting of the basin depocenter.

Following the early Burdigalian phase of uplift, a major late Burdigalian basin inversion occurred in TPB, leading to a dramatic increase of subsidence rate and accommodation space creation followed by another contractional event which induced,

in Langhian and early Serravallian, the underthrusting of the Ligurian and Adria margin units and the uplifting of TPB margins ([GNACCOLINI, 1968; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 1985; GNACCOLINI & ROSSI, 1994; PIANA & POLINO, 1994; CLARI *et alii*, 1995; MUTTI *et alii*, 1995; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019](#)).

In the eastern TPB, this event induced the local occurrence of angular unconformities during the Langhian ([ROSSI & CRAIG, 2016; ROSSI, 2017; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019](#)) and the northwestward progradations of slope and shelf sediments (Synthem TPB 3b) (Marne di Cessole, Siltiti di Gavi, Serravalle Fm) in Alto Monferrato and Borbera-Grue subdomains, making a basinward lateral transition to slope and turbidite deposits in Langhe (Cessole Fm., Cassinasco Fm. and Lequio Fm.). Synthem 3 bends with a widespread hiatus (i.e., D4 unconformity) and deposition of lower Tortonian outer shelf sediments (lower member of the Marne di S. Agata Fossili; see also [GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 1985, 2014](#)).

This Stop is dedicated to the observation of the D3b unconformity, bounding at the base the Synthem TPB 3b. D3b cuts the Miocene and Oligocene successions down to the Rigoroso Formation (Variano lithozone) of the underlying Synthem 1b. In front of Albarasca village, Langhian outer shelf sediments (Siltiti di Gavi) unconformably rest onto Oligocene (Rupelian) sandstones of the Variano lithozone. A lag deposit, made up of fragments of sandstones, marls and siliceous marls, locally occurs along the D3b basal erosional surface ([Fig. 15](#)).

Stop 1.2

Locality: Val Borbera.

44.720780,8.916722

Topic: The Middle Miocene succession: Siltiti di Gavi - Serravalle Formation.

In this Stop ([Fig. 16](#)) we can see the Middle Miocene succession of Borbera-Grue subdomain with the gradual transition from the Siltiti di Gavi to the Serravalle Formation.

The Siltiti di Gavi (middle-upper Langhian) consist of bioturbated marly siltites deposited in an outer shelf environment. In the upper part decimetre to meter thick layers of bioclastic sandstones rich in molluscs and red algae are intercalated.

Fig. 14 – Geological map of the southern Piemonte-Liguria area, with Itinerary and Stops of Day 1 and Day 2.

Fig. 15 – (a) Angular unconformity at the base of Siltiti da Gavi (SDG) cutting into the Variano lithozone of the Monastero Formation (RIO3b). SEV: Serravalle Fm. Locality; Piscine di Sorli. (b), (c) Detail of the angular unconformity (red line) followed by a basal lag with clasts of the underlying Early Miocene - Late Oligocene successions. Locality: Piscine di Sorli.)

The Serravalle Formation in the Borbera-Grue sub domain is characterized by an alternation of gray siltstones and sandstones passing to bioturbated bioclastic sandstones, organized in groups of layers of plurimetric to decametric thickness and characterized by the presence of large-scale cross-lamination (sandwaves). The transition between the two formations is gradual, without evidence of discontinuity.

Lunch at Borghetto Borbera.

Stop 1.3

Locality: Sottovalle.

44.652395,8.881689

Topic: TPB as an inverted Early Miocene basin, now involved in the Apennine belt; compressional tectonics and the Burdigalian basin reorganization.

During the very late Oligocene and the Early Miocene, the tectonic indentation of the European and Apulia continental margin caused the switch from transtensional to contractional and transpressional regime in the TPB, inducing inversion of a great number of tectonic structures (PIANA & POLINO, 1995; FALLETTI *et alii*, 1995; PIANA *et alii*, 1997; PIANA, 2000; FESTA *et alii*, 2005; PIANA *et alii*, 2006; ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; MAINO *et alii*, 2013; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019). This process was coeval with the transpressional tectonics recorded in Sardinia and southwestern Corsica (CARMIGNANI *et alii*, 2004).

In response to these major tectonic events, a number of regional scale unconformities developed throughout the Alps-Apennines syn-orogenic basins.

In the TPB, the D2 major regional unconformity formed in response to the above-described events. It is an angular unconformity which cuts into the siliceous member of the Montechiaro d'Acqui Fm. and Marne di Rigoroso Fm. (Alto Monferrato) and corresponds to a Chattian (or Aquitanian) - lower Burdigalian hiatus. In the deep-water settings (Langhe), it laterally grades to a correlative conformity, dated to the early Burdigalian (d'Atri *et al.*, 2015). The D2 discontinuity surface formed during the Burdigalian event and led to a major reshaping of the basin (D'ATRI *et alii*, 1997).

The succession deposited during step 2a (Synthem BTP 2) consists mainly of Burdigalian carbonate ramp deposits passing upward into deeper-water calcareous marls through glauconite-rich outer ramp condensed sediments (e.g. Visone Fm., in Alto Monferrato, D'ATRI, 1990a,b; D'ATRI *et alii*, 1997; PIANA *et alii*, 1997; D'ATRI *et alii*, 2015).

In the Alto Monferrato sub domain, the D2 corresponds to an angular unconformity (enhanced by a significant chronostratigraphic hiatus) at the base of Burdigalian shelf deposits of the Visone Fm., which rests on Chattian slope marls of the Rigoroso Fm and/or Aquitanian siliceous marls of the Montechiaro d'Acqui Fm. In the Lemme-Scrvia valley sector the shelf deposits of the Visone Formation are replaced by resedimented bioclastic sandstones of the Rocca Crovaglia Lithozone, a lenticular unit corresponding to a submarine incised valley fill. The basal part of the filling is made up of paraconglomerates with a pelitic-sandy matrix and clasts ranging from centimetres to several metres in size consisting of basement rocks, marly clasts, folded silicified marl blocks, clasts perforated by lithophagus

Fig. 16 – Northern (right) side of the Borbera valley between Vignole and Borghetto Borbera. In the southern slope of Monte Spineto, in front of Variano village, the transition from the outer shelf Siltiti di Gavi (SDG, Langhian) and the inner shelf sandstones of the Serravalle Fm. (Serravallian) is exposed. Stop 1.2 is located at the base of the cliff, just in front of it, on the left side of the stream.

organisms and bioclasts of a littoral/circalittoral environment (macroforaminifera, ostreids, pectinids, red algae, bryozoans). The succession continues with layers of medium to coarse grain-size bioclastic turbidite sandstones in thick and very thick layers, which become thinner, with finer grain size and with pelitic interlayers towards the top.

This Stop is dedicated to the view of Rocca Crovaglia Lithozone of the Visone Fm., which unconformably rests on the siliceous member of the Montechiaro d'Acqui Fm. or on the the Marne di Rigoroso fm., well exposed in the lower part of the Rocca Crovaglia southern slope (Fig. 17, Fig. 18, Fig. 19). Here in the Rupelian part of the Marne di Rigoroso Fm. decimetre to meter thick layers of cinerites (zeolitites) linked to a trachytic magmatism are present (D'ATRI & TATEO, 1994).

Stop 1.4

Locality: Carrosio.

44.660303,8.833732

Topic: D2 unconformity.

This Stop allows a more detailed and proximal observation of D2 unconformity (Fig. 20).

Relations with evidence of the early Burdigalian contractional tectonics found in other domains of TPB will be discussed here.

Stop 1.5

Locality: Bosio.

44.636947,8.781046

Topic: Early Oligocene transgression: the Molare Fm., from continental to shallow marine sedimentation.

The Alpine collisional tectonics induced the exhumation of the Alpine metamorphic units, the deepening of the foreland basins with the deposition of turbidite systems and, in the retroforeland, the onset of the epi-MesoAlpine basin (sensu MUTTI *et alii*, 1995).

In the more proximal part of the basin, near the uplifting areas of the Ligurian Alps, continental sediments (e.g. Breccie della Costa di Cravara) are locally preserved. These sediments would

be later unconformably covered by other continental to shallow marine sediments (i.e. Molare Fm.), after the onset of the early Oligocene transgression (TPB Synthem 1a).

The early Rupelian tectonic phase, mostly transpressional in the overall southern part of the Western Alps (DUMONT *et alii*, 2012), can be related in TPB to a local transtensional regime developed in the inner side of the uplifting Alpine belt.

The continuum of the collisional contractional tectonics (“Ligurian phase II” sensu MUTTI *et alii*, 1995, coeval with the westward movement of the Adriatic indenter, induced at shallow crustal levels a complex partitioning of transpressional and transtensional regime, synchronous with the main exhumation phase of the HP metamorphic units of the SW Alps, as largely described in literature (HOGERDUIJN STRATING, 1991; RUBATTO & SCAMBELLURI, 2003; CARRAPA *et alii*, 2003; FEDERICO *et alii*, 2004, 2005; VIGNAROLI, 2006; MAINO, 2009; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2008, 2009, 2010; ROSSI *et alii*, 2009; MOSCA *et alii*, 2010; ARGNANI, 2012; BEUCHER *et alii*, 2012; GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2014)

High-angle, synsedimentary faults, probably correlated to the rifting phase of the Balearic basin (REHAULT *et alii*, 1984), dissected the units of the TPB substratum in a series of fault blocks (MUTTI *et alii*, 2002). Anyway, in the northern edge of the Balearic-Ligurian rift, the stretching of the lithosphere was less pronounced, rapidly decreasing toward the North due to the hindering effect of the southern prolongation of the Ivrea high-density body (MAINO *et alii*, 2013). The gradual decrease of the rifting, and then of the incipient subduction rate, was partitioned by E-W, transpressive faults in the Ligurian Alps (e.g. LIVZ of PIANA *et alii*, 2006, see also GHIBAUDO *et alii*, 2019).

Consequently, in this domain a wide extensional regime did not developed, but a marked regional uplift occurred (JOURDAN *et alii*, 2013), followed by an intense regional denudation, which resulted, during the Rupelian, in widespread coarse-grained sedimentation (either continental or marine) over the exhumed basement (BERTOTTI *et alii*, 2006; VIGNAROLI *et alii*, 2010). A marked transgressive event (LORENZ, 1969; HACCARD *et alii*, 1972) occurred in the internal part of the Alpine belt. This occurred in an

Fig. 17 – Panoramic view on the southern slope of Rocca Crovaglia from Sottovalle-Rigoroso road. D2 unconformity separates the Rocca Crovaglia lithozone (VIS1b) of the Visone Fm. from the siliceous member of the Montechiaro d'Acqui Fm (MTH1) or directly the marls of the Rigoroso Fm. (RIO3) well exposed in the lower part of the slope.

Fig. 18 – Masseria Praga. Chaotic deposits present at the base of Rocca Crovaglia lithozone. To the right a block consisting of folded silicified marl.

Fig. 19 – Cinerite layer (black arrow) in the Marne di Rigoroso Fm., consisting of silty marls with intercalated turbidite layers. Locality: Sottovalle.

Fig. 20 – Lemme River near Carrosio. D2 unconformity (red line) separates the Rocca Crovaglia lithozone (VIS1b) from the marls of the upper member of the Marne di Rigoroso Fm. (RIO3).

overall geomorphological context marked by fast uplifting areas and adjoining throughs, which were characterized by subsidence rates highly variable through space and time.

In the TPB the Alpine tectonics induced the sedimentation of Synthem TPB 1, bounded at the base by the Unconformity D1 (lower part of Rupelian), which, in the southern part of the TPB, consists of a nonconformity surface between the bedrock (either metamorphic or non-metamorphic) and the overlying sedimentary successions. Synthem TPB1 begins with continental to shallow water Rupelian conglomerates and arenites (Molare Fm., [LORENZ, 1969](#); Savignone Fm., [BELLINZONA & BONI, 1971](#)) that grade to sandy and marly sediments, i.e. the lower part of Rigoroso Fm. ([GELATI, 1968](#)) in Alto Monferrato, and the Monastero Fm. ([BELLINZONA & BONI, 1971](#)) in the Borbera-Grue sub-domain.

The stop consists of two sites where the Rupelian Molare Fm can be observed.

The first one (Stop 1.5a, [Fig. 21](#)) is dedicated to the bioclastic coastal and fan-delta deposits (conglomerates, sandstones and siltites) of the Molare Fm. (MOR3), which were deposited during the last steps of the Stage 1a, just before the Rupelian drowning of the platform and the subsequent deposition of the Marne di Rigoroso.

The second one (Stop 1.5b, [Fig. 21d](#)) concerns the underlying and slightly older continental (fluvial and/or slope fan) deposits (conglomerate, and breccia with sandstone matrix, MOR 2). Clasts are made of metaophiolite, calcschist, marble, lime-

stone and dolostone. Sediments were deposited in narrow fault-bounded basins showing marked lateral facies changes (in composition and internal organization).

Stop 1.6

Locality: Eremiti pass.

44.600543,8.809135

Topic: The incipient continental sedimentation after the main Ligurian tectonic phase, Breccie della Costa di Cravara.

The Breccie della Costa di Cravara (late Eocene?-early Oligocene?) are a thick interval of continental breccias lying on the peridotite and serpentinite of the Voltri Massif in the sector between the Gorzente and Lemme valleys ([ALLASINAZ *et alii*, 1971](#); [CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008](#)). These breccias are unconformably overlain by the Rupelian Molare Formation, as can be observed in the upper Morsone Valley ([LORENZ, 1969](#); [LORENZ & REBORA, 1982](#)).

The Breccie della Costa di Cravara ([Fig. 22](#)) are heterometric breccias with angular to subrounded clasts, a few centimetres to several metres in size. The clast composition mirrors that of the ophiolite substrate: clasts are mainly composed of peridotite and serpentinite, and very minor metabasite. These breccias commonly lack any internal organization; only locally (Lago delle Ciocche) an ill-defined, metre-thick bedding can be observed. These breccias are characterized by a dark-green matrix, which becomes reddish when weathered, and can be interpreted as continental slope breccias

Fig. 21 – (a) Stop 1.5a. Fan-delta conglomerates and coastal bioclastic sandstones of the upper part of the Molare Formation (MOR 3 member). (b) Stop 1.5a. Detail of a microconglomerate bed with abundant, dark-green serpentinite clasts and bioclasts (pectinid bivalves). (c) Stop 1.5a. Bioturbated sediments of the MOR 3 member of the Molare Fm. Bedding surface of a sandstone layer preserving y-shaped crustacean burrows (*Thalassinoides*). (d) Stop 1.5b - Continental conglomerates and sandstones of the MOR2 member of the Molare Formation

Fig. 22 – (a) Panoramic view of the Breccia della Costa di Cravara (CRA) cropping out in the upper Morsone valley, Voltaggio. This unit lays on the peridotite and serpentinite of the Voltri Massif (VOM) and is unconformably overlain by the Molare Formation (MOR). (b) Breccia della Costa di Cravara cropping out near the Valico degli Eremiti. Note the lack of internal organization and the abundant blocks more than a meter in diameter (the height of the pine trees is about 8-10 metres). (c) Detail of the Breccia della Costa di Cravara cropping out near the Valico degli Eremiti, here composed of decimeter-sized, angular to subrounded blocks of peridotite and serpentinite, with a dark-green to reddish matrix.)

Day 2 : Crossing the “Ligurian Knot”: tectonic units between the Alps and the Apennine (Sestri-Voltaggio Zone)

Laura Crispini¹, Laura Federico², Giancarlo Molli²

Field Trip Route

Voltaggio, Passo della Bocchetta, Genova (Fig. 14).

Topics

During the second day of the excursion we will go through the innermost metamorphic units of the Ligurian Alps which are represented by the HP-LT units of the Voltri Massif (or Voltri Group, CHIESA *et alii*, 1975) and by three tectono- metamorphic units (Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit (CVMU), Gazzo-Isoverde Unit (GIU), Figogna Unit (FU) historically referred to and mapped as the Sestri-Voltaggio Zone (CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984). The Sestri Voltaggio Zone is a km-wide north-south oriented structural domain that includes tectono-metamorphic units of the Alpine belt and it is limited to the west by the HP-LT Voltri meta-ophiolite (through the Sestri-Voltaggio Line), to the North is overlain by the TPB sediments and to the east is in contact with very low grade Ligurian units (Fig. 23).

The Sestri-Voltaggio Zone (SVZ) was defined in the 60s referring to a complex of rocks, occurring from Sestri Ponente to Voltaggio in a 5-6 km-wide N-S strip (GÖRLER & IBBEKEN, 1964) and the great complexity of the area has been attracting the interest of generations of geologists. The SVZ western contact with the HP-LT Voltri Massif (usually referred to as the Sestri-Voltaggio Line) has been considered as the boundary between the Alps and the Apennines for a long time. ELTER & PERTUSATI (1973) questioned its significance as a boundary between the two chains, pointing out that the Sestri - Voltaggio line cuts across structural directions and emphasizing that the structures with opposite vergence, of which it seems to represent a line of symmetry, are partly posterior to the age of the line itself. They see the Sestri - Voltaggio line as an early fracture, with

the characteristics of a “transform” fault, that connects with the Voghera - Pavia line and the Giudicarie line.

Since the 80s other researchers have described the Sestri-Voltaggio Line as a contact between units with different metamorphic conditions, later tilted to the vertical by late-orogenic tectonics (CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984; CAPPONI, 1991) or as an extensional tectonic surface placing low pressure on high pressure metamorphic units (HOOGERDIJN STRATING, 1991). CRISPINI & CAPPONI (2001) and CRISPINI *et alii* (2009) highlighted the evolution of the role of the Sestri-Voltaggio Line, changing from a boundary between different tectono-metamorphic units to a dextral transcurrent system, in the different stages of the Alpine and late Alpine evolution.

Actually the Sestri Voltaggio Zone can be considered as a high strain zone or fault zone and it can be better referred to as Sestri-Voltaggio Fault Zone. In the present-day map view it marks the contact among units of different paleogeographic derivation and re-equilibrated at different P-T metamorphic conditions.

The cross-section of Fig. 23b shows the simplified structural architecture at shallow level of the area across the innermost units of the Ligurian Alps (Voltri Massif, Sestri-Voltaggio Zone and Flysch units). The cross-section is representative of the geometric stacking of the units, of the relationships among the units and their internal structural arrangement. The poorly exposed contacts among the tectonic units are generally steeply dipping to the east so that the HP-LT units are the lowermost units and the very low grade Flysch units the uppermost units of the tectonic pile; the Antola Unit is in the top structural position, with a low-dipping tectonic contact (Fig. 24). At the outcrop scale, the boundaries among the metamorphic units are folded shear zones commonly reactivated by strike-slip faults with the same longitudinal trend. Moreover the area close to the Sestri-Voltaggio Line can be considered as a high strain zone and is characterized by intense shearing and fracturing (Fig. 25).

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Fig. 23 – (a) Sketch map of the Alps-Apennines boundary, after *CAPPONI et alii* (2009a). (b) Geologic cross section (WNW-ESE) of the metamorphic basement across the Sestri Voltaggio Line, after *CAPPONI & CRISPINI* (2008).

Fig. 24 – Schematic summary of the Sestri-Voltaggio Zone and its tectonic story (after *MOLLI et alii*, 2010). After the main orogenic syn-metamorphic Alpine phases, in the Ligurian Alps, a regional top to E-NE backthrusting phase that involves the Oligocene TPB successions and the metamorphic basement is described for the Ligurian Alps and testifies to a major tectonic activity lasting up to the Oligocene (*D'ATRI et alii*, 1997; *CAPPONI et alii*, 2001, 2009a). The principal tectonic activity of the Sestri-Voltaggio Fault Zone possibly lasted up to Late Oligocene-early Miocene as the related subsidiary structures involve the Aquitanian-Burdigalian TPB deposits. The SVZ and the backthrusts can be inserted in a same tectonic framework where SVZ acted as a dextral tear fault in the general migration of the Ligurian Alps towards NE-N.

Deformation	Tectonic event	Fabric	Metamorphism	Vergence
D ₁ /D ₂	subduction	tight to isoclinal similar not cylindrical folds and related schistosity	blueschist facies low T	unconstrained
Sth ₂	exhumation-uplift of the metamorphic units and nappe emplacement	reverse, ductile to brittle-ductile shear zones	limit greenschist/ pumpellyite - actinolite facies metamorphism	top to S-SW
D ₃	nappe emplacement	open to close sub- cylindrical folds	albite + chlorite + epidote	top to NW
Sth ₃	nappe emplacement	low-angle reverse and normal faults	albite + chlorite + epidote	top to NW
D ₄	backthrusting	open folds thrust faults	zeolite facies	top to E-NE
D ₁ /D ₂	subduction	tight to isoclinal similar not cylindrical folds and related schistosity	pumpellyite - actinolite facies	unconstrained
Sth ₂	exhumation-uplift of the metamorphic units and nappe emplacement	reverse, ductile to brittle-ductile shear zones	albite + chlorite + epidote	top to S-SW
D ₃	nappe emplacement	open to close sub- cylindrical folds	albite + chlorite + epidote	top to NW
Sth ₃	nappe emplacement	low-angle reverse and normal faults	albite + chlorite + epidote	top to NW
D ₄	backthrusting	open folds thrust faults	zeolite facies	top to E-NE

Fig. 25 – Schematic synthesis of the relationships between deformations and metamorphism for the SVZ units (modified from CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008).

Fig. 26 – Location of Stop 2.1 (yellow dot), after CAPPONI & CRISPINI (2008). CRA–Eocene-Oligocene Sedimentary Breccia, MG–Greenschist Metagabbro with eclogitic relics, SNV–HP-LT serpentinite, LHP–peridotite with HP-LT overprint.

Stop 2.1

Locality: Panorama view west of Eremiti Pass.

44.595003, 8.793280

Topic: The emerging HP-LT alpine basement: mantle peridotite with metamorphic overprint (Erro-Tobbio or Voltri Unit) next to continental sediments (Cravara Breccia).

The aim of this stop is to get a panoramic view of the scenario at the transition between the sedimentary cover of the TPB and the metamorphic substrate. We are located in the northern sector of the Voltri Massif close to the contact with the overlying sedimentary successions of the TPB and the adjacent units of the SVZ (Fig. 26).

In this outcrop the Voltri Massif is represented by outcrops of mantle peridotite (lithospheric spinel lherzolites, reactive spinel peridotites, plagioclase-rich peridotites with pyroxenite and dunite bodies, Fig. 27) and serpentinitised peridotite with

minor lenses and dykes of metagabbro, known in literature as “Erro-Tobbio peridotite”- ET (CHIESA *et alii*, 1975; PICCARDO & VISSERS, 2007) and ascribed to the Voltri tectono-metamorphic Unit for the Alpine metamorphic features (CAPPONI *et alii*, 2016).

In spite of the HP-LT Alpine overprint the Voltri-ET peridotite preserves metre- to-kilometer-scale volumes of preserved peridotite that retain mantle textures and mineral assemblages (spinel-to plagioclase paragenesis), thus allowing the study of their pre-Alpine mantle evolution (PICCARDO & VISSERS, 2007; PADOVANO *et alii*, 2015). The peridotite bodies are enclosed in HP-LT serpentinite; there is a gradual transition from partially-serpentinized peridotite tectonites to serpentinite mylonites with an antigorite + magnetite + titanian-clinohumite + chlorite + diopside foliation. In the north-eastern sector of the Voltri Massif (close to the SVZ) partly serpentinitised peridotites are variably sheared along a steeply dipping N-S regional schistosity. Serpentinities enclose bodies of metagabbros and metasediments; these bodies are variable in size and record different peak conditions (from eclogite to blueschist facies) and different P-T paths (Fig. 28). Moreover, disrupted parts of the Palmaro-Caffarella Unit are sheared and boudinaged inside the Voltri Unit following the regional foliation. This tectonic setting has been interpreted as assembled in a subduction domain at the interface between the converging plates (“fossil” serpentinite-subduction channel) and possibly matching the characteristics of a tectonic mélange (MALATESTA *et alii*, 2012).

Stop 2.2

Locality: Morsone River Valley, Voltaggio.

44.614866, 8.824549

Topic: Eo-Oligocene tectonics in TPB sediments and metamorphic basement.

We drive back towards the village of Voltaggio following the Morsone River and crossing road cuts of the sedimentary de-

Fig. 27 – (a), (b) The Voltri (Erro-Tobbio) peridotite. Lherzolite showing granular to low strain tectonic fabric. The main deformation fabric in the outcrop is related to mantle shear zones. (c), (d) Continental Cravara Breccia (view to the SE, Mt Tobbio in the back), clasts are mainly composed of Voltri Massif serpentinite.)

Fig. 28 – The eastern sector of the Voltri Massif, interpreted as a fossil subduction channel. A sheared matrix of serpentinite and calcschists encloses bodies of different lithologies, with different metamorphic evolution. Modified after [MALATESTA et alii \(2012\)](#).

Fig. 30 – Geologic Sketch map of the Stop 2.2 with the cross sections traces B and C.

Fig. 31 – (a) Panoramic view of the TPB conglomerates with steeply dipping bedding (detail of the section B of Fig. 30). (b) Tilted Bedding (dip 60 to the west) in the TPB sediments close to fault zone. (c) Detail of HP-LT metagabbro (eclogite-blueschist Voltri Unit) boulders in the Morsone river (possibly derived from clasts of the TPB basal sediments). (d) E-W strike slip fault in dolomitic limestone of the Gazzo-Isoverde Unit.)

Fig. 32 – Simplified reconstruction of the structures that characterize the main outcrops of the three units in the Sestri-Voltaggio Zone. Stereograms summarize the main structural elements of the Zone. 3D-cartoon are not to scale (after CRISPINI & CAPPONI, 2001).

istic dotting, hence the term used by French authors of *Calcaires pointillés* (Fig. 33). The dots are in places aligned and elongated forming a stretching lineation.

At the microscale, deformed 30-40 micron calcite grains are observed, immersed in a microcrystalline matrix, relicts of an original detrital pellet texture or relicts of crinoid segments. In some samples, red-orange radiolarian shells were found, which in contrast to the carbonate matrix appear undeformed. They are concentrated along thin phyllosilicate films or at intergranular sites where dissolution is concentrated.

In the sheared siliceous limestones, quartz concentrated in small lenses parallel to the foliation and locally shows a weak oblique grain shape fabric.

Stop 2.4

Locality: Ponte San Giorgio, along the SP160 road, South of Voltaggio

44.591445, 8.858338

Topic: Composition and structures of the Metamorphic Oceanic units: multiphase deformation and metamorphism of the alpine orogenic cycle in blueschist facies metagabbro.

In this Stop (Fig. 14, Fig. 34) we observe the characteristics of metagabbro of the blueschist facies of the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit. It is possible to observe structures formed during metamorphic conditions of the HT-LP ocean floor, foliations produced during metamorphic conditions of the Alpine Pumpellyite-Blueschist facies and late alpine brittle structures.

The outcrop consists of a metamorphic coarse to fine grained

Fe-Ti Oxide-gabbro which preserve cross-cutting relations between primary (igneous) and secondary plastic (pre-alpine and alpine) and brittle deformation structures. The primary foliation is cut by a basaltic dyke (Fig. 35).

The Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit igneous basement is mainly composed by Ol-Gabbro and Fe-Ti Oxide-gabbro with dykes/veins of diorite and plagiogranite, by ophiolitic tectonic breccia and by pillow lava. The Ponte San Giorgio is one of the most extensive body of metagabbro in the SVZ enclosed in foliated serpentinite and metasediments (Fig. 36).

It is composed in general by Fe-Ti oxide gabbro with subordinate dioritic compositions; it shows a compositional and/or grain size layering (varying from centimeter to millimeter) and a texture varying from isotropic to protomylonite and blastomylonite. Polyphasic intrusions of dykelets/veins with quartz-dioritic to plagiogranitic composition are frequent. The dykelets are in places deformed by HT-LP (“ocean floor metamorphism”) plastic shear zone (CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984), or may cut the HT-LP foliation.

Doleritic dykes up to plurimetric in thickness, associated with brown hornblende/epidote veins, often contain fragments of the host foliated gabbro. The Alpine HP-LT mineralogical assemblage consists of albite + Na-anfibole +/- Na- and Na-Ca-clinopyroxene +/- chlorite +/- lawsonite +/- epidote +/- pumpellyite +/- titanite and is generally well developed (CABELLA *et alii*, 1994; CORTESOGNO *et alii*, 2002) along shear zones (Fig. 37) or mimetically replacing original igneous minerals (e.g.; fine grained Alpine albite and lawsonite preserve the crystallographic orientation of the primary plagioclase).

Fig. 33 – (a) Panoramic view of folded and foliated metamorphic crystalline limestone on the front of a disused quarry (Cava Cementir, 1996) view to the south. S1 to S3 refers to the main foliations described in the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit. (b) Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit Low-T blueschist limestone with steeply dipping regional foliation (composite foliation). (c) Meter scale mullions parallel to fold axis. (d) Detail of the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit limestone: Foliation surface with dark grey spots hence the name *Calcaire pointillés* of French Alpine literature). (e) Thin section photomicrograph of the calc-schist. Multiple foliation is composed by fine grained white micas, calcite, opaque minerals. The mica outline a composite S1 and S2 foliation.

Fig. 34 – Location of Stop 2.4, geological map by [CAPPONI & CRISPINI \(2008\)](#).

Fig. 35 – (a) Historic photo ('90) of the E-W road cut wall. (b) Sketch of the metagabbro structures (drawing by L. Cortesogno '90).

Fig. 36 – Varitextured metagabbro of the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit with details of different textures and degree of deformation. (a) Magmatic porphyroclastic structure. (b) Ultramylonitic structure.

Fig. 37 – Photomicrograph of the mylonitic structure of the Ponte San Giorgio metagabbro (PPL).

Fig. 38 – Panoramic view across the SVZ looking towards SW.

Stop 2.5

Locality: Bocchetta Pass, panoramic viewpoint.

44.550165, 8.888145

Topic: Panoramic view across the Sestri-Voltaggio Zone (lunch).

The purpose of this Stop (Fig. 14, Fig. 38) is to take a panoramic view of the section through the collisional knot and have lunch! The stop is characterized by schist of the pumpellyite-actinolite facies Figogna Unit, i.e. the low metamorphic equivalent of the Palombini shale in the oceanic cover sequence. In the area the Figogna Unit shale enclose meter to decameter-scale lenses of pillow lava, associated to metacherts and limestone.

Stop 2.6

Locality: Lencisa-Ceranesi.

44.493179, 8.849983

Topic: SVZ Tectonic unit of the continental margin: metamorphic limestone and dolostone of the Gazzo Isoverde Unit and its contact with Blueschist oceanic unit (serpentinite and pillow basalt). Limestone: 44.491422, 8.845844 ; Serpentinite 44.492639, 8.850960

The aim of this Stop (Fig. 14, Fig. 39) is to make observations and discussions on the geological features and structural architecture of the Gazzo-Isoverde Unit unit and its contact with boundary units. From the village of Lencisa we descend along the main road toward the south where we find various limited exposition of limestone and dolomitic limestone.

The Lencisa-Mt. Torbi represents one of the 4 areas within the SVZ where the Gazzo-Isoverde Unit sedimentary succession outcrops with the best continuity along the slopes of Mt. Torbi. The Gazzo-Isoverde Unit unit is characterized by a Mesozoic (Trias-Lias) continental shelf sequence (CORTESOGNO & HACCARD, 1984; LUALDI, 1991; CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008) of neritic dolostone (“dolomie di Monte Gazzo” formation, Upper Carnian?-Norian) overlain by an alternation of thick, partially recrystallized, fossiliferous limestone beds with thin shale layers (“calcarei di Galaneto” formation, Rhaetian-Hettangian) grading upward into massive, partially recrystallized limestone beds with chert nodules (“calcarei di Lencisa” formation, Sinemurian-Pliensbachian). This turbiditic sequence is covered by hemipelagic black shales

with thin recrystallized calcareous interbeds (“metargilliti di Bessega” Formation, Middle Liassic-Malm?) (Fig. 39).

The structures and deformation phases are the same described for the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte Unit. The bulk chemical composition and low-T metamorphism preclude the growth of good diagnostic metamorphic minerals in the Gazzo-Isoverde Unit lithologies, so the available evaluation of the PT conditions has been deduced from the structural and cartographic relationships with the neighboring oceanic units or from microstructures in calcite.

The main regional structure of the Lencisa-Mt. Torbi Gazzo-Isoverde Unit has been interpreted as a major synclinal antiform (D2 or D3) with N-S (0° to 30°) trending fold axis with variable dip, and with the axial plane dipping to the E. The structural architecture is complicated by shear and fault zones commonly present at the dolostone-limestone contact. At outcrop scale, the more calcareous lithologies, despite their more or less extensive recrystallisation, preserve the original sedimentary features and remnants of fossiliferous forms.

The marly and dolomitic limestone beds display a spaced pressure solution cleavage (Fig. 40), pelitic interbeds show a penetrative axial-planar slaty cleavage. The more recrystallised limestone (Calcarei di Lencisa) shows zones of high strain concentration with extensive shear deformation occurring in the limbs of the main folds. In these zones we can observe transposition of isoclinal/intrafoliar folds along the main regional foliation and mylonitic structures, such as asymmetric foliation boudinage, domino structures, sheath folds (Fig. 41). At the microscale, the micritic limestone is dynamically recrystallized with evidence of grain size reduction and rotation recrystallization, twinned calcite ribbons are enclosed in a matrix of fine grained calcite showing oblique grain shape fabrics. Calcite fibers occur in pressure fringes around opaques minerals and quartz grains.

Going back to Lencisa Moving eastwards along the road cut, strongly foliated serpentinite with a cataclastic to mylonitic structure can be observed for a few metres (Fig. 42), with the main foliation subvertical to strongly dipping towards the east, in contact with metabasalts (pillow lava) alternating with phyllite schists belonging to the Cravasco-Voltaggio-Montenotte unit.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 39 – (a) Geological map with the location of Stop 2.6 (orange dot) (after [CAPPONI & CRISPINI, 2008](#)). (b) Stratigraphic column of the Gazzo-Isoverde Unit sequence, after [VANOSI \(1991\)](#).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 40 – Gazzo-Isoverde Unit limestone along the main road. Fold hinge zone show high angle relationships between two foliations (S2 and S0+S1).

Fig. 41 – High strain zones in limestones of the Gazzo-Isuverde Unit. (a) Mylonitic foliation and foliation boudinage at the outcrop scale. (b) - (d) Photomicrographs of mylonitic structures in the recrystallised Gazzo-Isuverde Unit micritic limestone in high strain zones.

Fig. 42 – Highly deformed foliated serpentinite with folds and S-C structures.

Day 3 : The Ligurian ophiolites and the inner Northern Apennines

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Field Trip Route

Varese Ligure - Passo del Bracco - Montaretto - Bonassola - Rocchetta Vara (Fig. 43).

Topics

Introduction to geology of the Bracco area, orogenic structures of the ophiolitic unit, ophiolite stratigraphy, petrology and pre-orogenic deformation, ophicalcite quarries.

In this third day of excursion we will have the opportunity to see some character of the uppermost units of the NA and in particular of the Internal Ligurian units along the coast and in the hinterland of La Spezia. This area represents the part of Apennines with the longest “modern” geological investigation dating back to the early 19th century. We present an introduction to geology of the Bracco area, orogenic structures of the ophiolitic unit, ophiolite stratigraphy, petrology and pre-orogenic deformation, including the visit of a ophicalcite quarry.

The east Liguria represents a key region for the studies of the Ligurian Tethys ophiolites having a special role in the historical and modern geological knowledge. The area was visited by BRONGNIART (1821) and one century later by STEINMANN (1927).

In the early 1960s BAILEY & McCALLIEN (1963) analyzed the local geology following the problems related to the original association of pillow lava, serpentinites and cherts at that time recognized as the “Steinmann Trinity”, (BERNOULLI *et alii*, 2003). Later, ABBATE (1969), and above all DECANDIA & ELTER (1969, 1972), addressed the peculiarity of the Ligurian ophiolites. They described a major unconformity between mantle rocks and overlying basalts, tectonosedimentary breccias (ophicalcites and ophigabbros) and sediments. Moreover, DECANDIA & ELTER (1969) firstly suggested the interpretation of mantle and gabbro tectonic fabrics as related to low-angle extensional shearing and mantle exhumation connected with tectonic processes predating the emplacement of basalts, being therefore

at the forefront of the concepts that are today proposed to understand continental breakup at magma-poor rifted margins and ultra slow spreading ridges (BOILLOT & WINTERER, 1987; MANATSCHAL & MÜNTENER, 2009; MOLLI, 2020). The Bracco-Levanto and nearby areas were furthermore the object of key papers on the petrology of mantle (BEZZI & PICCARDO, 1971; PICCARDO, 1977; RAMPONE *et alii*, 1998; PICCARDO *et alii*, 2014), geochemistry of ophiolitic magmatism (FERRARA *et alii*, 1976; BECCALUVA *et alii*, 1980; SERRI, 1980), ocean-floor metamorphism (SPOONER & FYFE, 1973; CORTESOGNO *et alii*, 1975, 1994; BONATTI *et alii*, 1976; CORTESOGNO & LUCCHETTI, 1984; TRIBUZIO *et alii*, 1997) and stratigraphy-sedimentology of ocean-floor deposits and mineralizations and their connection with the tectonic environment (BONATTI *et alii*, 1976; BARRETT & SPOONER, 1977; FOLK & McBRIDE, 1978; BARRETT, 1982; CORTESOGNO *et alii*, 1987; ZACCARINI & GARUTI, 2008).

The geology of the Bracco-Levanto area, ground of the first three stops of the day, is represented in the map of Fig. 44.

Stop 3.1

Locality: Mattarana quarry.

44.2472144,9.5881516

Topic: introduction to the main lithotypes of the Bracco area.

The main lithotypes in the Bracco area are represented by gabbroic cumulates and serpentinitized mantle peridotites (Fig. 45). Primary contacts between the plutonic rocks and the peridotite testify the intrusive character of the gabbro body within mantle rocks.

The cumulates are mainly represented by olivine-bearing gabbros (as observed along the road), but also by olivine-rich cumulates like in this quarry.

In this first outcrop, two lenses of ultramafic cumulates are interlayered with olivine-bearing gabbros. The quarry consists of pl+cpx-bearing dunites to mela-troctolites and troctolites, in which the primary igneous structures are observable. Spinel and clinopyroxene are commonly preserved, whereas olivine and plagioclase are partially or totally replaced by serpentine + Fe-oxide phases + chlorite ± tremolite and prehnite + chlorite ± hydrogrossular, respectively.

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Fig. 43 – Geological map of eastern Liguria, with Itinerary and Day 3 stops.

Fig. 44 – Geological map of the Bonassola-Levanto area. Based on 1:5000 scale GM mapping (1990-1994), [DECANDIA & ELTER \(1972\)](#) and [CORTESOGNO *et alii* \(1987\)](#), with stop locations.

Fig. 45 – a) Serpentinized lherzolite showing tectonite-fabric at an angle with pirossenite-rich layers. Deformation fabric related to mantle shear zones pre-dating the gabbro, 165 Ma old intrusions; b) gabbro showing magmatic layering defined by clinopyroxene, olivine and plagioclase-rich layers; c) ultramaphic cumulate (melatroctolite); d) typical ophicalcite, polyphasic fault rock, related to pre-orogenic “oceanic” detachment fault; e,f) high temperature gabbro-mylonite showing gneissic porphyroclastic structures defined by cpx-rich and plagioclase-rich layers, f) at microscopic-scale, cross-polarized light.

Ultramafic cumulates have olivine (commonly about 85 % by volume) and accessory spinel as cumulus phases, and minor poikilitic plagioclase and clinopyroxene. Mafic minerals are highly magnesian: olivine has 88 forsterite mol% and clinopyroxene has mg# value ($Mg/(Mg+Fe_{tot})$) of 90. These cumulates are the early products of a fractional crystallization process starting from N-MORB-type liquids (SERRI, 1980; SERRI *et alii*, 1989; TRIBUZIO *et alii*, 2000, 2016).

Igneous layering made up by grain-size variations of the cumulus olivine can be observed, together with thin chromite grains parallel to the layering and huge clinopyroxene crystals. Igneous layering is also in places shown by variations in olivine modal percentages. In pegmatoid patches, cumulates locally develop harrisitic structures ("Christmas-tree", BEZZI & PICCARDO, 1971). These magmatic structures, defined by skeletal symmetric parallel olivine intergrown, are interpreted as a result of decreasing diffusion rate and increasing growth rate, as it is commonly found in rapidly cooling magmas.

Stop 3.2

Locality: Montaretto.

44.1975385, 9.5885825

Topic: ophicalcite quarries and supra-ophiolite sedimentary cover.

Close to village of Montaretto (north of Levanto) we may observe the character of Ligurian sedimentary cover (Cherts and Palombini limestone) locally covering basaltic breccias and pillow lava but also elsewhere gabbros or serpentinites (Fig. 45). Moving back we'll see in a quarry a typical Ligurian ophicalcite.

The ophicalcites (Fig. 45d) locally known as Levanto breccias (but also by the commercial names of Rosso or Verde Levanto) represent the uppermost part of serpentinites. Ophicalcites consist of two main components occurring in variable amounts: subangular to subrounded serpentinite (or rarely gabbro, or rodingite) clasts and a white or pink carbonate matrix. Near the underlying serpentinites the matrix is scarce and the clast distribution indicates that the fragments are in-situ or were little reworked. Higher levels show a more abundant matrix, sometimes with dispersed clasts; grading, lamination and imbrication of clasts suggest their sedimentary transport (Framura breccia, ABBATE *et alii*, 1980). The serpentinite clasts are often red due to oxidation of magnetite to hematite. Most of the pink matrix is a microcrystalline calcite (and more rarely dolomite and ankerite) and scattered hematite, filling the fissures and wide fractures among or within the serpentinite blocks (sedimentary or neptunian dykes). Sedimentary features of the carbonate mud can be recognized (e.g. grading, lamination and geopetal structures) but no micro- or macro-fossils have been found so far. The present interpretation of the carbonate matrix suggests that it was a muddy marine sediment, in part remobilized by hydrothermal processes.

From the structural point of view, the most interesting features of the ophicalcite can be observed within some clasts in the uppermost "sedimentary" levels, and even better in the lowermost parts just at the top of the serpentinite body. Two different types of structures can be recognized, both characterized by polyphasic evolution. The early generation of structures is represented by plastic shear zones, whereas the latter consists of polyphasic fracturing. According to Cortesogno *et al.* (1987),

Molli (1995) and Treves and Harper (1996), the general evolution of ophicalcites can be reconstructed as follows (Fig. 46):

- intrusion of gabbroic dykes and bodies in peridotite (previously affected by mantle deformation in shear zone) (at 165-161 Ma Tribuzio *et al.*, 2016);
- early "crustal" shearing ($T > 800^{\circ}\text{C}$): mylonitic foliation (Ol + Cpx + Ti-Prg + Pl in ultramafics and Pl + Cpx \pm Ti-Prg? \pm Ol in metagabbros);
- onset of serpentinization and second generation of shearing ($T < 550^{\circ}\text{C}$): mylonitic serpentinite-structures (Serp + Ta \pm Tr \pm Chl \pm Mag) in ultramafics and rodingitic mineral assemblages in gabbros;
- fractures systems; the older veins are filled with serpentine, whereas the most diffuse contain calcite with less abundant hematite, talc, chlorite, andradite and tremolite, developed under hydrothermal conditions;
- development of sedimentary breccias, neptunian dykes. Hydrothermal phenomena were still active, together with sedimentary reworking.

The overall evolution of these rocks showing plastic to brittle deformation during progressively lower temperature and pressure conditions suggests their genesis as fault rocks during the uprise of the mantle toward the ocean floor. This interpretation of the ophicalcite was drawn and discussed in the frame of a low angle normal faulting at the beginning of the Seventies (Decandia and Elter, 1969) and it is now recognized at slow- or ultra-slow spreading mid-ocean ridges (in the so called "oceanic core complex", WHITNEY *et alii*, 2013 and references therein).

Stop 3.3

Locality: Bonassola.

44.1803756, 9.5843923

Topic: gabbros with high temperature shear zones crosscut by hornblende veins and albitite.

The stop winds along the eastern shoreline of Bonassola village. Map and cross section Fig. 47 shows the main geologic features of the area. The large scale deformation geometries consist of an open north-east facing syncline (cross-sections in Fig. 48) dissected by later high angle normal and oblique-slip faults.

The gabbroic massif of Bonassola displays intrusive contacts with serpentinized mantle rocks, which crop out along the coast toward Levanto. Both gabbros and serpentinites are covered by ophiolitic mono- and polygenic breccias well exposed in the M. Rossola area. The outcrop consists of Mg-gabbros which evidence cross-cutting relations between igneous, plastic and brittle deformation structures. The dominant rock-type consists of coarse grained gabbros composed of euhedral plagioclase (about 55%) and olivine (minor than 20% in volume), and subhedral to poikilitic clinopyroxene. Plagioclase-rich pegmatoid patches are frequently found.

Compositional layering characterized by modal and/or grain size variations is recognizable in some places (Fig. 49a). A pervasive high temperature foliation at low angle with respect to the compositional layering can be observed (Fig. 49b). In particular, the most widespread rock type is a porphyroclastic coarse-grained protomylonite. Dragging of the foliation in higher strain

Fig. 46 – The ophicalcite-structure evolution record of exhumation of “oceanic” detachment fault with progressive increase of fluid-rock hydrothermal interaction.

zones, asymmetric porphyroclasts and mylonitic folds can be locally recognized (Fig. 49c).

At microscopic scale the foliation is defined by recrystallized pyroxene and plagioclase grains. Arrays of systematic fractures filled with amphibole (\pm plagioclase) are widespread throughout the area (Fig. 49d). The sets strike quite uniformly NW-SE and dip steeply to NE and SW. Most veins are nearly planar and range in length from a few millimeters to decimeters, whereas their width generally does not exceed a few millimeters.

The amphibole veins are mainly of mode-2 (hybrid-type cracks) with displacement up to few millimeters. When cross-cut by amphibole veins, the igneous clinopyroxene in the wall-rock is partially replaced by amphibole, due to fluid diffusion away from fracture (up to few centimeters). In particular this transformation is well evident when amphibole veins crosscut the pegmatoid gabbros (Fig. 49e).

Locally albitite dykelets (commonly of centimetric thickness) with irregular contacts (GARZETTI *et alii*, 2009) characterized by coarse-grained hornblende rich reaction zones (Fig. 49f). These dykelets represent residual melts that were injected before complete solidification of the host gabbro. The albitites with sharp planar boundaries are inferred to have formed subsequently, when the host gabbro was under a brittle tectonic regime. U-Pb zircon dating by laser ablation ICP-MS provides evidence for two distinct albitite pulses separated by a period of magmatic inactivity of the order of millions of years (GARZETTI *et alii*, 2009). The long time interval between solidification of the gabbro and its uplift to sub-seafloor conditions, dated by the first and second generation of albitites, respectively, indicates a slow exhumation rate for the host gabbro.

Late fractures filled with quartz (\pm Fe-sulphides) can be ob-

served and locally reworks the amphibole veins. Sporadic calcite \pm prehnite fractures crosscut both amphibole and quartz veins.

Stop 3.4

Locality: Rocchetta Vara.

44.2478061, 9.7547667

Topic: Ligurian sopra-ophiolitic sedimentary sequence.

In this stop we can observe lithotypes referable to the Bracco unit (Fig. 50), resting below the overlying Gottero unit in the eastern limb of a regional scale synform structures in which the Vara valley is cut.

The locality was visited (Fig. 51) and firstly figured by BRONGNIART (1821) in his famous paper “*Sur le Gisement ou position relative des Ophiolites, Euphotides, Jaspes, etc. dans quelques parties des Apennins*”. In this paper the term Ophiolite was introduced in the geological literature.

The area is the site of a past quarrying activity on cherts. It is possible to observe an overturned sequence formed by serpentinitized ultramafics, ophicalcites, ophiolitic breccias called M.Zenone Breccia, cherts, Calpionella limestone and Palombini shales. The M. Zenone breccia is interpreted as a debris flow deposit locally thick one hundred metres. It is made of monogenic gabbroic clasts of variable size, surrounded by sandy or silty gabbroic chloritic matrix. Some of the gabbros clasts show evidence of HT shearing. The sedimentary contact with the overlying cherts is witnessed by the intercalation of ophiolitic debris, arenitic in size, within the cherts (Fig. 52). At the top of ophiolitic breccias BAUMGARTNER (1984) recognized an early to late Callovian radiolarian assemblage, whereas a late Oxfordian assemblage is recognized by CHIARI *et alii* (2000) in the quarry (20 m up to the base of cherts).

Fig. 47 – Geological map of the Bonassola-Levanto area. Based on 1:5000 scale author's mapping (1990-1994), [DECANDIA & ELTER \(1972\)](#) and [CORTESOGNO *et alii* \(1987\)](#), in [MOLLI \(2020\)](#).

Fig. 48 – (a) Geological cross-sections for trace see Fig. 47; (b) Reconstructed interpretative sections of the former OCT at the time of deposition of Palombini shales (early Cretaceous) based on retrodeformation of the geological structures in the Bonassola-Levanto area. Vertical and horizontal scale based on observed thickness of lithologies and retrodeformation of the orogenic and late orogenic structures.

Fig. 49 – (a) Coarse-grained clinopyroxene rich gabbros with a weak modal and grain size layering. (b) HT mylonitic foliation sub-parallel to the igneous layering of the gabbro. (c) Mylonitic fold in a high strain domain of the gabbro body. (d) Parallel fracture-sets filled with hornblende, crosscutting at high angle the HT foliation of the host gabbro. Hornblende is also found as coronas around (sheared) clinopyroxenes in the gabbro; (e) Hornblende vein crosscutting a pegmatoid gabbro. Clinopyroxene of the host gabbro is replaced by hornblende for a few mm due to fluid diffusion away from the fracture. (f) Elongated albitite body showing sharp planar boundaries with the host gabbro. The albitite crosscuts the microgabbro body in the host gabbro at a high angle.

Fig. 50 – Geological map of the Brugnato-Rocchetta Vara area. After [MONTEFORTI & RAGGI \(1975\)](#).

Fig. 51 – Profile and present view of the right side of the Gravignola creek published in [BRONGNIART \(1821\)](#). On the left (SW) the highest ridge is made up of serpentinite, the saddle on gabbro and gabbro breccia whereas the cliff on the right (NE-side) is within a 170 m thick radiolarian cherts.

Fig. 52 – (a) Gabbro-breccia made up of poor-sorted gabbro debris including clasts of undeformed coarse grained gabbro (*eufotidi* Auctt.) and high temperature gabbro-mylonite in a fine grained gabbro-derived matrix (M. Zenone breccia). (b) Stratigraphic contact between ophiolites here represented by ophiolitic sandstone, mainly gabbro-derived) and radiolarian cherts in an overturned sequence.

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